

Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge Solutions' Gains

D2.3: Use case requirements and specifications, dimensions and target KPIs

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
4G	4th Generation mobile network
5G	5th Generation mobile network
AI	Artificial intelligence
API	Application programming interface
CPE	Customer premises equipment
CPU	Central processing unit
CSR	Corporate social responsibility
EMQ	Erlang/enterprise/elastic MQTT
ERDF	European regional development fund
E2E	End-to-end
GCSE	General certificate of secondary education
GDPR	General data protection regulation
GPU	Graphics processing unit
ID	Identification
IoT	Internet of things
KFT	Knowledge facilitation tool
KPI	Key performance indicator
LoRaWAN	Long range wide area network
LoS	Line of sight
ML	Machine learning
MNO	Mobile network operator
MQTT	Message queuing telemetry transport
MTBF	Mean time between failures
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
NR	Next radio
PLF	Precision livestock farming
RAM	Random access memory
RFID	Radio frequency identification
RGB	Red-green-blue

RTT	Round trip time
SRL	Societal readiness level
TBD	To be determined
TRL	Technology readiness level
UC	Use case
UHD	Ultra high definition
URL	Uniform resource locator
Wi-Fi	Wireless fidelity

1 Executive Summary

The XGain project seeks to provide access to smart XG, last-mile connectivity, and edge computing solutions for relevant stakeholders such as municipalities, policymakers, farmers, foresters and their associations by fostering sustainable and inclusive development in rural, coastal, and sub-urban areas. The development of a knowledge facilitation tool (KFT) is the project's objective. This tool will assist the relevant stakeholders in creating and evaluating business models and making informed decisions in selecting technology ecosystems that increase the systemic resilience and energy efficiency of their regions, contribute to the mitigation of climate change effects, and reduce the digital inequalities among different groups of people.

This deliverable, belonging to WP2 which targets to designing methods to identify the needs of farmers, associations and communities, provides an initial in-depth analysis of each use case (UC) in which the KFT will be evaluated. The appropriate UC information is collected based on the needs of end-users, analysed through co-creation processes in Task 2.1 and the social, digital and environmental concepts, extracted by Task 2.2 through interviews and questionnaire surveys. Specifically, important factors that define each UC are analysed appropriately. These include: a) the baseline functionality, b) operational environment (including information about terrain, socio-economic context and demographic profile and co-existing services in the considered region), c) expected evolution of the operational environment in the foreseeable future, d) demonstration of UC storyline, e) technological solution mixture (connectivity and computation devices that are needed), f) main non-functional and functional requirements and the expected values of key performance indicators (KPIs).

Subsequently, the extensive collection of UC information that belongs to different rural services' sectors (such as remote communities, farming, agriculture, aquaculture, forestry etc.), terrains and meteorological conditions is necessary for the KFT application in different rural fields of interest. The gathering of the characteristics of each UC is of utmost importance to incorporate appropriate functionalities into the KFT to be able to deal with them such as the weather's and terrains' impact. These factors support the functional generalisation in the application of the proposed decision support engine and helps the KFT architecture design in Task 2.4.

2 Introduction

This deliverable presents the collection of UC requirements and specifications for connectivity and edge technology enablers³. This collection leads the design of the specific UC driven solutions, and the KFT decision support mechanisms. Particularly, details about the operational environment and description of required services, identifying socio-economic and environmental restrictions emerging in the targeted operational area, are provided and constitute pillars of designing the general mechanisms of the tool.

On the technological front, the requirements, which can be different across UCs depending on the service, delve, initially, into the details of availability, reliability and performance, while also capturing service coverage and scalability aspects. Moreover, aspects related to the demographic/operational evolution and socio-economic context in the considered region are presented. Suitable technical KPIs and target values are identified for each UC, that will also later drive the technical performance evaluation, and validation of the delivered technological propositions. Finally, in order to capture the overall demand of connectivity and processing capabilities in the UC area, the co-existing services are depicted. This information is valuable for the provision of generalisable solutions being able to service not only the specific UC demands, but also wider area's demands.

The detailed information of UC characteristics presented in this deliverable serves as a basis for the trials in the field in WP5.

2.1 Mapping XGain Outputs

In Table 1 the content of current deliverable is described.

Table 1: Adherence to XGain GA deliverable & tasks description.

XGain GA Component Title	XGain GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D2.3 Use case requirements and specifications, dimensions and target KPIs			
Report on UC requirements and specifications for connectivity and edge technology enablers.			
TASKS			
Task 2.3	Task 2.3 will specify the non-functional and functional requirements for the overall XGain propositions. Intended to lead the design of the specific use case driven solutions, and the decision support mechanisms and tool, T2.3 will investigate in detail the operational environment and	Sections 3-8	Each section provides a detailed analysis of UC requirements and specifications for connectivity and edge technology enablers, identifying also possible socio-economic and environmental restrictions.

³ Generally, the UC configuration includes the end devices, connectivity technologies and processing devices.

	service level specificities at hand, identifying socio-economic and environmental restrictions emerging in the targeted operational environments.		
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2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable presents the outcomes from the requirements gathering of 6 UCs under the task T2.3 'XGain Use Case Requirements and Specifications for Connectivity and Edge Technology Enablers'. More specifically the document is divided logically into six main sections based on the six different UCs. Each UC section includes the same sub-sections, but with different content according to the specific UC. The structure of each section is as follows:

- 1) UC ID: UC Title
 - Baseline functionality
(Brief description of the UC including a high-level description of the envisioned service i.e., general context, application functionality, types of users/stakeholders, different usage scenarios / storylines (if multiple))
 In this sub-section the specific role of each UC partner is provided according to Table 2: UC partners and their role.
 - Operational environment
(Description of the overall operational environment including terrain / topology aspects that may have an impact on the technology mixture e.g., mountains, seaside, etc., demographic aspects e.g., user population density, age characteristics)
 - Terrain/Topology
 - Socio-economic context - Demographic profile
 - Co-existing services
(Description of any other services expected to co-exist with the service corresponding to the use case. The intention is to potentially capture the overall demand for connectivity and processing capabilities in the area, beyond the specific use case, that would need to be taken into account when considering the viability of a certain technological mixture)
 - Evolution
(Description of expected evolution of the operational environment in the foreseeable future e.g., population density dynamics, broader infrastructure developments etc.)
 - Demonstration storyline
(Description of the envisioned storyline for a demonstration of this use case)
 - Envisioned solution
 - Technology mixture
(Description of the end-to-end (E2E) technology mixture currently envisioned for the use case. This should include connectivity technology as well as edge processing solutions envisioned.)
 - System level topology

(A simple illustration of the system level topology including network and compute equipment, the envisioned interconnection, user equipment, etc. This must be end-to-end.)

- Sequence diagram – Service interaction
(A simple sequence diagram illustrating the exchange and processing of data between the various system nodes (depicted in system level topology above))

○ Requirements

- Functional requirements
(Lists of UC functional requirements. This should include all main functionalities of the corresponding service e.g., data collection, processing. This will later support UC validation/verification)
- Non-functional requirements
 - Socio-economic
In this sub-section UC requirements and their priority are provided according to Table 3 based on the values of Table 4.
 - Environmental (including Terrain/Topology)
In this sub-section UC requirements and their priority are provided according Table 3 based on the values of Table 4.
 - Performance-KPIs
In this sub-section technical UC KPI definition and target values are provided according to Table 5. In general, the list of measured KPIs may differ across UCs based on the corresponding service requirements.

○ Societal Requirements

- Societal and technology readiness level (SRL & TRL values)⁴
- Organigram
(Provision of a simple but clear organigram – including names/email contact – of all those working on and in the use case organisation/set-up)
- Site-specificity
(Is the UC site specific? <yes/no> If yes, <in which ways? Add short description> Note: site-specificity refers to not (easily) replicable or scalable technological or design-related solutions, and socio-environmental circumstances and contexts, which make a given technological intervention unique and tailor-made/locally adapted at the same time.)
- Ethical Considerations & Social Innovation
(Does the use case/organisation/company work with corporate social responsibility (CSR) guidelines or criteria, which will be relevant for workshop and knowledge alliance? < Describe>)
- ISO 26000:2010⁵
(Select the most relevant normative/ethical aspects of social responsibility, presented in Figure 1, for the workshop(s) and according to organisational CSR (if applicable): <Selection

⁴ Source and further information on SRLs and TRLs:

https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/isa/files/technology_readiness_revisited_-_icegov2020.pdf

⁵ Source and further information: <https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/store/en/PUB100258.pdf> and <https://www.iso.org/iso-26000-social-responsibility.html>

according to list below Figure 2 and Figure 3 (multiple entries perfectly possible and preferred)>)

- Social Conflicts, Use-case related
(Indicate briefly already known and potentially foreseeable conflicts of interest or socio-political conflicts between the pre-identified stakeholder groups. For instance, between policy-makers or their institutions in terms of priorities or political orientation; between farmer cooperatives, environmental non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and business, etc.)
- Vulnerability & potentially excluded stakeholders
(Indicate any already known or foreseeable vulnerable groups with minor representation in the stakeholder mapping (so far) and/or presence in the on-site/online workshops.)

Figure 1: Social responsibility: 7 core subjects.

[Source: <https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/store/en/PUB100258.pdf>]

Core subjects and issues	Addressed in subclause
Core subject: Organizational governance	6.2
Core subject: Human rights	6.3
Issue 1: Due diligence	6.3.3
Issue 2: Human rights risk situations	6.3.4
Issue 3: Avoidance of complicity	6.3.5
Issue 4: Resolving grievances	6.3.6
Issue 5: Discrimination and vulnerable groups	6.3.7
Issue 6: Civil and political rights	6.3.8
Issue 7: Economic, social and cultural rights	6.3.9
Issue 8: Fundamental principles and rights at work	6.3.10
Core subject: Labour practices	6.4
Issue 1: Employment and employment relationships	6.4.3
Issue 2: Conditions of work and social protection	6.4.4
Issue 3: Social dialogue	6.4.5
Issue 4: Health and safety at work	6.4.6
Issue 5: Human development and training in the workplace	6.4.7
Core subject: The environment	6.5
Issue 1: Prevention of pollution	6.5.3
Issue 2: Sustainable resource use	6.5.4
Issue 3: Climate change mitigation and adaptation	6.5.5
Issue 4: Protection of the environment, biodiversity and restoration of natural habitats	6.5.6

Figure 2: Core Principles of ISO 26000:2010: Part 1.
 [Source: <https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/store/en/PUB100258.pdf>]

Core subjects and issues	Addressed in subclause
Core subject: Fair operating practices	6.6
Issue 1: Anti-corruption	6.6.3
Issue 2: Responsible political involvement	6.6.4
Issue 3: Fair competition	6.6.5
Issue 4: Promoting social responsibility in the value chain	6.6.6
Issue 5: Respect for property rights	6.6.7
Core subject: Consumer issues	6.7
Issue 1: Fair marketing, factual and unbiased information and fair contractual practices	6.7.3
Issue 2: Protecting consumers' health and safety	6.7.4
Issue 3: Sustainable consumption	6.7.5
Issue 4: Consumer service, support, and complaint and dispute resolution	6.7.6
Issue 5: Consumer data protection and privacy	6.7.7
Issue 6: Access to essential services	6.7.8
Issue 7: Education and awareness	6.7.9
Core subject: Community involvement and development	6.8
Issue 1: Community involvement	6.8.3
Issue 2: Education and culture	6.8.4
Issue 3: Employment creation and skills development	6.8.5
Issue 4: Technology development and access	6.8.6
Issue 5: Wealth and income creation	6.8.7
Issue 6: Health	6.8.8
Issue 7: Social investment	6.8.9

Figure 3: Core Principles of ISO 26000:2010: Part 2
 [Source: <https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/store/en/PUB100258.pdf>].

2) UC templates of tables that will be presented

In Table 2 the name of the partners and their specific role will be presented, while in Table 3 specific requirements, their priority levels (shown in Table 4) and a brief description of them will be collected. Finally, in Table 5 the corresponding technical KPIs with their description are depicted. These KPIs include the connectivity or processing segments or both for each UC and will be measured in trials.

Table 2: UC partners and their role.

Partner	Role

Table 3: UC requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement Priority	Description

Table 4: Priority levels for UC requirements.

Priority level	Requirement priority
Mandatory	MUST
High priority	SHOULD
Preferred but not necessary	COULD
It can be postponed and suggested for future execution	WOULD

Table 5: UC technical KPI presentation.

KPIs	Description
Network latency	Measure the E2E round-trip time (RTT) of data exchanged by pinging different point of the network infrastructure
Network throughput	Obtain measurements of the downlink/uplink communication link bandwidth.
Jitter	Measure the variation in the delay of received packets.
Resource utilisation	Monitor CPU/GPU/RAM usage of processing devices.
E2E response time	Time between user ⁶ request generated and service response received at the use
Processing response time	Measure the time that a processing device needs to process the data
Power consumption	Power consumption of infrastructure
Service availability	Ratio of time the service is responsive and available to users
Service reliability	Percentage of successfully processed data within the expected processing time
Scale	Total number of end devices
Coverage	Served geographical area
Cost	Cost of infrastructure

⁶ The ‘user’ term in the KPI description is substituted with ‘end device’ if no human user interacts with the system.

3 UC 1: Rural Community Services (Spain)

3.1 Baseline Functionality

The access to state-of-the-art technologies for radio access, like 5th generation mobile network (5G), is sparse or even non-existent in rural areas. Yet, especially in these remote areas dedicated to agriculture and other typical rural services, incorporating innovative technologies and machinery can be very beneficial for the productivity, quality and return value of rural services. An example of an innovative use of technologies, both in cities and rural areas, are drones. Equipped with sensors or even actuators, these unmanned, remote-controlled devices introduce a great variety of functionalities and potential benefits. The use of drones and similar technologies, however, requires powerful and fast connectivity to unlock their full potential. Real-time high-definition transmission of video is just one possible scenario in which 5G is necessary to satisfy the technical requirements. This is why the presence of such radio technology is very important for rural areas, yet there is a great gap between the coverage seen in cities and remote areas. Another reason for justifying the use of 5G to enable drone use cases in rural/remote areas is the fact that in towns and cities there are strict regulations for the operation of drones, which make it difficult to train the use of these devices.

As such, in the Spanish pilot, we aim to deliver a space in a rural area that can be used to work and play with drones without any restrictions and having all the necessary radio and edge technologies to implement any type of services that might be provided. The Partner that is responsible for this UC is i2CAT as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Spanish UC: Partners and their role.

Partner	Role
i2CAT	Infrastructure and testing environment provider, technical partner for support to the use case execution (radio access + computation)

3.2 Operational Environment

The Spanish pilot is executed in an area close to Mora la Nova, Catalunya. This remote area features a large warehouse (around 70m*100m) surrounded by plantations. Both the spaces inside and outside the warehouse are intended to be used for the pilot. During the pilot, the warehouse will be equipped with Wi-Fi and 5G Next Radio (NR) devices to provide connectivity over a private network to users, as well as dedicated edge servers to host services. Outside, another 5G base station (in small cell format) will be available to provide outdoor 5G NR connectivity. The outdoor base station, just like the indoor one, will be connected to the edge computation devices inside the warehouse.

3.2.1 Terrain/Topology

The pilot site (“Molló”) is located in Mora la Nova, uphill next to the Ebro River, as shown in Figure 4. In Figure 5, on the other hand, we can see the warehouse and the surrounding fields/plantations. The warehouse that features the 5G laboratory and testbed, is located at a height of 65 m over sea level on a plain field with a slight slope that leads descends towards the Ebro River, located at a distance of 765 m. The river, with a width of around 120 m, separates the pilot site from the neighbouring town Mora d’Ebre, located further upstream at a distance of around 3 Km. While the area around the warehouse can be considered plain, there are some hills close by that feature peaks of up to 140 m over sea level. Next to the warehouse, the vegetation is relatively

scarce featuring trees of around 4-5 m of height adorning the access roads. Northwest of the warehouse are the closes plantations (orchard) with dense foliage. Finally, a small forest is located to the east-southeast.

Figure 4: Spanish UC: Topological map of the pilot area

Figure 5: Spanish UC: Satellite view of the pilot area that includes the warehouse (laboratories) and the surrounding fields

3.2.2 Socio-Economic Context - Demographic Profile

The closest village for which demographic data⁷ is available, at a 5-minute drive from the pilot site, is Mora la Nova, which is also the name of the municipality in which the pilot is located. Table 7 and Table 8 show the general and per age group population information respectively, about the Mora la Nova in 2022 which size is 15.93 Km².

Table 7: Spanish UC: General population details for Mora la Nova

Location	Municipality of Mora la Nova (2022)
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⁷ www.idescat.cat.

Population	3198
Population density (inhabitants per Km²)	200.8/Km ²

Table 8: Spanish UC: Population details by age group for Mora la Nova.

Age group	Share (%)	Total
0-14	14.57	466
15-64	64.85	2074
65-84	16.29	521
85+	4.28	137

Education⁸

Table 9 presents the education levels for Mora la Nova.

Table 9: Spanish UC: Education level in 2021.

Education Level	Share (%)	Total
Low	54.3	1726
Medium	21.5	687
High	24.2	773

Employment

Table 10 features an overview of the employment statistics for the pilot municipality based on the information that is provided in the same link as above.

Table 10: Spanish UC: Employment statistics for Mora la Nova

Type	Share (%)	Total
Employed Population	44.4	1173
Unemployed Population	8.9	234

⁸ In the corresponding tables, in whole document, we assume three main levels of educational attainment: low (less than primary, primary and lower secondary education), medium (upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education) and high (tertiary education i.e. education provided by universities and other higher education institutions) as these are determined in https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Educational_attainment_statistics.

Disability Pensioners	2.5	66
Retired Population	19.9	459
Students	5.8	153
Population with other inactivity status⁹	21.02	555

3.2.3 Co-existing Services

The region in which the pilot will be executed, features agriculture using many plantations (fruits, vegetables), but also other types of services. This includes tourism and logistics. While the pilot is directed towards showcasing how beneficial state-of-the-art infrastructure can be for the usage of drones, other potential uses include equipping harvesting machines with these technologies to improve their capacities and introduce concepts like livestock management or crop monitoring. This is speaking for the agricultural sector. The tourism and logistics sectors both could also potentially benefit from state-of-the-art technologies, but in different ways. The logistic sector could be very much interested in the use of drones for infrastructure inspection. As such, connectivity and processing capacities are both interesting options for the sector. The tourist sector, on the other hand, might benefit in a very different way, for example by enabling the use of augmented or virtual reality equipment in key sites (e.g., ancient ruins, medieval castles, etc.) to provide an augmented experience to visitors.

3.3 Evolution

The current pilot site features already the key technologies for the drone use case that is to be showcased. The infrastructure features additionally other types of connectivity and processing capabilities that are not directly used in the use case, but might be used for evaluation purposes (4G, Wi-Fi, distributed computing, wireless backhauling). Following the co-creation workshop held in 2023 and the upcoming collaborative activities with stakeholders, we anticipate gaining a clear understanding of how to make a drone operations centre appealing to stakeholders and how the centre can evolve to meet their evolving needs. Based on the feedback received thus far, it appears that established farmers seeking innovation, service providers interested in incorporating drones into their offerings, and a demographic known as "knowmads" could potentially utilize the centre's resources. Knowmads are a new generation of workers who are nomadic knowledge workers, adept at working digitally, creatively, and flexibly across various environments and contexts. The use of state-of-the-art technologies like 5G in a rural environment, could motivate them to migrate into these regions and this could lead to further developing the drone operations centre to feature dedicated spaces to get in touch with digital technologies and to use them. Attracting young people to the region is key to fostering a sustainable demography.

Within the project the infrastructure will be extended from just laboratory spaces with Wi-Fi connectivity, to a 5G-enabled laboratory that features a large indoor space with 5G connectivity, as well as outdoor connectivity. This operational environment will be able to satisfy the drone operation needs (drones connected over 5G), but

⁹ 1.) This data is taken from the government statistics, but without explanation of the exact composition 2.) According to the definition: "In the last group, all economically active persons who are not included in the previous categories are included, such as non-schooled minors, examination candidates, those who rely on charitable benefits or assistance, etc."

it can also be considered a working space or playground to get in touch with the 5G technology. From here, potentially many services and use cases emerge for long-term usage, but also for sporadic use of the facilities, and it will be key to listen to stakeholders and understand their needs.

3.4 Demonstration Storyline

While the pilot cannot demonstrate a full-time available drone operation centre, punctual use of drones is foreseen to showcase the drone and 5G technologies, in the form of a demo or specific event. While the lab is designed in such a way that it does provide a playground to operate and test the 5G connectivity with drones or other devices without any restrictions, the necessary subcontracting of a drone operator and the limited budget for this purpose only allow for a limited number of drone activities that can be executed during the pilot duration. The specific activities and scope of said demos would need to be determined in conversations with the drone operator that will be subcontracted by i2CAT. The potential use cases that seem reasonable at the current stage are indoor drone demonstrations, like a drone race, remote indoor infrastructure checks, or training sessions for drone operation. Outdoor demonstrations could evolve around media content creation for dissemination purposes (e.g., fly-overs over the area to create promotional videos), flying over nearby fields to monitor the state (plantation surveillance or crop monitoring), or infrastructure monitoring of the warehouse, to name a few. The possible scenarios will depend on the capacities of the drone operator and the coverage range of the 5G network that will be deployed on-site. i2CAT will try to align the drone-demonstrations with potential local events that take place in the area in order to maximize synergies with the local stakeholder community.

Beyond the demonstration evolving around the use of drones, the drone centre also can offer the 5G technology for a wider, more generic use by local stakeholders. The concept of a 5G laboratory and 5G-enabled space for other services (education, entertainment, etc.) allows us to target additional demonstrations where the XGain project can offer the 5G connectivity to stakeholders for specific events.

3.5 Envisioned Solution

3.5.1 Technology Mixture

The appropriate technology mixture is presented below:

- At the radio access, the use case will have access to 5G NR. We will be using spectrum assigned to us by the Spanish ministry, which can be up to 40 MHz in the band n77. The radios are connected to the networking infrastructure that is composed of switches and routers for outbound connectivity, all connected over fibre and dedicated ethernet.
- To facilitate service deployment in close proximity to users, edge computing nodes are connected to the same network infrastructure, resulting in minimal latency between the radio users and the compute nodes. This edge platform is achieved through an OpenStack cluster, which includes nodes located in different geographical locations within the pilot area.
- The drone operator might rely on the computing nodes as specified, or might bring its own computing nodes as an alternative. The specifications of such nodes are not known at the time of writing this deliverable, but could be similar to the infrastructure nodes, but with additional graphic processing units

for video processing. We expect a small form-factor device like a Jetson Nano¹⁰, or Jetson Orin¹¹ to be used.

3.5.2 System Level Topology

Figure 6 shows a diagram of a system level topology for a private 5G network that could be used for the UC, including different layers of edge processing capacities in which different types of services could be deployed. The alternative to this topology that is considered for the UC execution as a backup, is a public 5G network, where the edge processing capacities are not available, and where applications must run on dedicated hardware or in a cloud environment.

Figure 6: Spanish UC: System level topology for a private 5G network deployment that offers radio access and edge computing capacities.

3.5.3 Sequence Diagram – Service Interactions

The sequence diagram for the Spanish scenario, which involves a private 5G network, including radio access network and edge processing capabilities, is depicted in Figure 7. Note that the drone centre use case per se could offer different types of services. The example shown here is just a tentative scenario.

In such scenario, a drone captures an image via camera, which is pre-processed at the drone itself, sent over the 5G network that offers low latency and high throughput to the edge, where the actual heavy image processing is performed. This processing requires of dedicated edge computing capacities. Such processing is performed by a dedicated application that could be placed either in the near or far edge layers.

¹⁰ <https://developer.nvidia.com/embedded/jetson-nano-developer-kit>

¹¹ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/autonomous-machines/embedded-systems/jetson-orin/>

Figure 7: Spanish UC: Sequence diagram for a tentative drone use case that features video streaming.

The example shown, whose sequence diagram is presented in Figure 7, is the most exhaustive one, in the sense that all possible features of a generic 5G network are used. However, based on the previous experiments performed with drones in the pilot site, let us highlight that it is the least likely one: it has been observed that drone operators often just use the radio access connectivity to connect with their hardware deployed on site or a service located in the cloud, rather than at the edge. This is because for the full scenario shown in Figure 6: Spanish UC: System level topology for a private 5G network deployment that offers radio access and edge computing capacities., application development, integration and deployment at the edge are necessary, which requires time and effort. For this UC, there is no budget foreseen to pay for such activities as part of the subcontracting of a drone centre for the demo / trial. Also, there exists the possibility of executing the UC with a public 5G network without edge processing capacities, rather than a private network, which is an equally relevant option in rural areas.

3.6 Requirements

3.6.1 Functional Requirements

A list of functional requirements that are considered in this UC is provided below:

- A drone **MUST** be available for the pilot.
- The drone **MUST** be able to be equipped with a 5G modem or customer premises equipment (CPE) that is capable of connecting the pilot-site 5G NR network.
- The drone **MUST** be able to be equipped with a camera at least supporting high-definition resolution.
- The 5G-NR network **MUST** provide sufficient coverage to allow the drone to fly up to a certain limit in the horizontal and vertical plane, both indoors and outdoors.
- The 5G-NR network **MUST** provide low latency and sufficient throughput to be able to transmit an ultra-high definition (UHD) quality encoded video stream.
- The 5G network **COULD** provide edge computing capacities, if a specific service needs it, but **MUST** provide internet connectivity and/or allow to connect a custom device to the network.
- The 5G network **SHOULD** expose important network and computation metrics, if these are made available by the 5G network implementation.

- The 5G network **MUST** have dedicated resources only for the drone use case, i.e., either a dedicated slice or guaranteed radio resources.
- A computing infrastructure **MUST** be available in the pilot area in order to process the images captured by the drone and display them in the application.

The pilot project will utilise specific equipment, including two Cablefree small cells¹² for 5G NR connectivity. One of these will be installed indoors, within the warehouse, while the other will be situated outdoors. The specific models are:

- CableFree Emerald Small Cell (Indoor)
- CableFree Emerald Small Cell (Outdoor)

Further, either modems or CPEs will be used to provide 5G connectivity. Since the specific models will depend on how the integration progresses with the 5G network and the drone operator, it is not possible to determine which exact models will be used. It is expected that either Quectel modems¹³ or industrial CPEs from vendors like Milesight or Sunwave will be used.

For executing the pilot, two additional computational elements are required: the server on which the 5G core will be running (to which the radio nodes connect), and the server hosting the service showcased during the pilot. This latter device potentially will be provided by the drone operator. If such a server does not get deployed, i2CAT can provide alternative computation elements (no GPU-based services are expected).

- Intel NUC11PAHi5 Barebone i5-1135G7. Such device could host both the 5G core and the service.
- Raspberry Pi 4 Model B.

3.6.2 Non-functional Requirements

A list of non-functional requirements for this UC is provided below:

- During the use case execution, the network and all the resources (radio/edge) **MUST** be stable with high availability.
- Non-5G users of the use case **MUST** not have access to any of the data that is generated or consumed by the drones.
- Servers **COULD** store large amount of data. This data could be used to train predictive machine learning (ML) models.

3.6.2.1 Socio-economic

In Table 11 the corresponding socio-economic requirements are shown.

Table 11: Spanish UC: Socio-economic requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Durability	SHOULD	The system should be designed considering long-lasting capabilities and scalability.
Accessibility	MUST	The system must present the information in a comprehensible and interpretable format.

¹² <https://www.cablefree.net/5g-lte/5g-small-cell-base-station-radios/>

¹³ <https://www.quectel.com/product-category/5g-modules>

Technologies	MUST	Use case must assist in reducing the workload, personnel and monetary expenses for professionals, government entities, and academics.
Security	MUST	Security access to the system should not be allowed within the network

3.6.2.2 Environmental (including Terrain/Topology)

In Table 12 the corresponding environmental (including terrain/topology) requirements are presented. It needs to be highlighted that given the pilot involves drone operations, there are some important limitations. On one hand, the meteorological conditions need to be adequate. In case of rainfall, high temperatures or wind, the drone operation could be problematic. While the rainfall is very sparse and the region is not known for strong winds, the heat can be an issue during summer. Figure 8 shows the historic rainfall and temperatures over the year, though it should be noted that during the last years temperatures have gone up and rainfall has decreased. The high temperatures can affect the hardware mounted on the drones and also the 5G base station, which means that in intense summer heat scenarios, no tests can be performed to protect the hardware. Sporadic days with strong wind gusts have been observed, which should be avoided for testing and validation purposes. To monitor the weather in real time, a meteorological station was installed close to the pilot site and can be accessed publicly¹⁴.

Figure 8: Spanish UC: Weather observations data from Mora la Nova

Table 12: Spanish UC: Environmental, terrain and topology requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Weather and climate conditions	MUST	Drone flights rely on favourable atmospheric conditions. The factors that may obstruct the outdoor trials are severe weather (wind, heavy precipitation, thunder) and milder phenomena that will worsen the quality of the images (mist, dazzling light, clouds).
Temperature and Humidity	MUST	Drones must be able to operate within a specific temperature and humidity range to ensure optimal performance. In extreme temperatures, the radio or computing hardware on drones could stop working properly.

¹⁴ <https://www.wunderground.com/dashboard/pws/IMRALA5>

Restricted airspace	MUST	Drones only can fly in non-restricted areas. Rural areas are usually not affected by such restrictions, however a newly declared nearby heliport could affect the airspace permissions for outdoor testing (not affecting the indoor tests).
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3.6.2.3 Performance – Key Performance Indicators

Finally, in Table 13 the performance KPIs with corresponding target values are provided.

Table 13: Spanish UC: KPIs.

KPIs	Description	Specific Target
Network latency	Measure the E2E round-trip time (RTT) of data exchanged by pinging different point of the network infrastructure (in ms).	< 50 ms
Network throughput	Obtain measurements of the downlink/uplink communication link bandwidth (in Mbps).	>= 25 Mbps
Jitter	Measure the variation in the delay of received packets (in ms).	< 50 ms
Resource utilisation	Monitor CPU/GPU/RAM usage of processing devices (%).	TBD (Depends on the service provided by the drone operator)
E2E response time	Time between user request generated and service response received at the user (in ms).	< 100 ms
Processing response time	Measure the time that a processing device needs to process the data (in sec)	TBD (Depends on the service provided by the drone operator)
Power consumption	Power consumption of infrastructure (in W)	About 400 W
Service availability	Ratio of time the service is responsive and available to users	TBD (Depends on the service provided by the drone operator)
Service reliability	Percentage of successfully processed data within the expected processing time	TBD (Depends on the service provided by the drone operator)
Scale	Total number of end devices	2 drones at most
Coverage (outdoor)	Outdoor coverage area (in Km ²)	0.01 Km ² (100mx100mx50m)
Coverage (indoor)	Indoor coverage area (in Km ²)	0.0021 Km ² (70mx30mx10m)
Cost	Cost of infrastructure (in €)	About 9K €

3.7 Societal Requirements

3.7.1 Societal and Technology Readiness Level

UC1 targets to SRL6 and TRL6.

3.7.2 Organigram

- August Betzler, Technical & Project Manager (main contact for technical questions, workshop organizer, lab management, UC management) of i2CAT, august.betzler@i2cat.net
- Pau Pamplona, Project Manager (contact for WP6 activities, policy and social innovation) of i2CAT, pau.pamplona@i2cat.net
- Joan Josep Aleixendri, R&D Engineer (contact for technical questions) of i2CAT, joan.aleixendri@i2cat.net
- Adrián Pino, R&D Engineer (contact for technical questions) of i2CAT, adrian.pino@i2cat.net

3.7.3 Site Specificity

The use case has site specificity, because requires of a 5G network to achieve high throughput and low latency in a rural environment. For this either a private or public network are the options considered, which are not available in other rural areas or i2CAT laboratories. The area in which the UC takes place is representative for remote farming areas, which makes this UC also very site-specific. An existing ecosystem of stakeholders from the rural & public sector can help to push any co-creation tasks and activities in the region.

3.7.4 Ethical Considerations & Social Innovation

The UC does not work with CSR guidelines or criteria.

3.7.5 ISO 26000:2010

The most relevant normative/ethical aspects of social responsibility, based on the use case selection, for the workshop(s) and according to organisational CSR are 6.8: 6.8.3, 6.8.6

3.7.6 Social Conflicts, Use-case Related

No conflicts of interest or socio-political conflicts are foreseen between the stakeholder groups.

3.7.7 Vulnerability & Potentially Excluded Stakeholders

No vulnerable groups with minor representation in the stakeholder mapping (so far) and/or presence in the workshops are foreseen.

4 UC 2: e-Health (Greece)

4.1 Baseline Functionality

Katerina is an 86-year-old widow who lives alone in a single-story house in a rural area in Central Macedonia of Greece. The nearest town is about an hour away. The network infrastructure was installed decades ago and has not been upgraded since then, resulting in the network quality and speed being quite degraded. She does not know how to use a computer, or a smartphone, and she is generally not familiar with digital technologies.

Apart from the hypertension for which she receives medication, she does not have any other medical condition. Her doctor wants her to be very consistent in taking her medication and points out to her every time how important water intake is. E-Health Robot is going to act as a virtual caregiver to monitor and give advice to older adults. It comes with some interventions that enhance well-being which are focused on cognitive exercise, nutritional guidance, physical exercise and social recommendations. These interventions are projected through a mini-projector that comes with the e-Health robot and with a speakerphone that is able to receive commands from the user and also speak to them. The interventions that projected are advice (day insights), quizzes, games that enhance memory, nutritional advice that focus on fibres and social recommendation in order to encourage socialisation.

Also, e-Health robot is equipped with a camera for emotion recognition. The results of these activities are processed daily with a user model that is pseudonymised and synchronised with CAPTAIN's server.

Although there are various local events organised since it is quite a touristic area, her house is at a high altitude where snow is present most days of the year and is hence difficult to attend. Katerina would like to virtually attend some events related to her interests and boost her wellness through cognitive games and quizzes. E-Health robot is going to suggest online workshops that are closer to older adults' interests. Optionally, she would like to participate in social interactions with other users.

The Partners and their role in this UC are shown in Table 14.

Table 14: Greek UC: Partners and their role.

Partner	Role
CAPTAIN	Provide e-Health robot.
	Develop the additional components for 5G connectivity and provide technical support for the system installation.
	Provide support to RDFCM for technical issues arising during the pilot.
RDFCM	Identification of stakeholders and participants recruitment based on the identified inclusion/exclusion criteria.
	Handle the ethics application.
	Day-to-day communications with participants for feedback collection.
ICCS	Conducting a simulation with CAPTAIN Box device on the laboratory with 5G connectivity and ICOM's network link.

4.2 Operational Environment

The location in which the UC will be presented is in the Region of Central Macedonia, on the outskirts of the town of Thessaloniki, approximately 25 Km from the city centre (see Figure 9). The CAPTAIN Box devices are going to be installed in older adults' homes within the area that is described below.

4.2.1 Terrain/Topology

It is called Vasilika, and it is located in a plain, the valley of the Anthemounda river. The total population of the area is 4115¹⁵. Around Vasilika are the mountains of Hortiatis 1200m and 5.5Km apart, Lanaris 800m and 9.35 Km apart, Prophet Ilias 550m and 4.34 Km apart and Agios Yannis 700m and 2.81 Km apart¹⁶. There are also forests such as those of Lanaris and Prophet Ilias. In Vasilika there are many streams and waterfalls and dams such as those of Vasilika and Agios Antonios at a distance of 6Km. Moreover, except for the terrain characteristics, the weather conditions do not cause any problems.

Located at an elevation of 202.32 meters above sea level, Central Macedonia has a humid subtropical, no dry season climate (Classification: Cfa (C = mild temperate, f = no distinct dry season, a = hot summer). The city's yearly temperature is 17.37°C and it is 0.35% higher than Greece's averages. Central Macedonia typically receives about 27.7 millimetres of precipitation and has 66.19 rainy days (18.13% of the time) annually¹⁷.

Figure 9: Greek UC: The area of Vasilika.

¹⁵ Source: ELSTAT, Population - Residential Census Results 2021 - <https://www.statistics.gr/el/2021-census-res-pop-results>

¹⁶ Distances were measured based on the central square of the village and the top of each mountain via google earth with the distance calculator tool

¹⁷ <https://weatherandclimate.com/greece/central-macedonia>

4.2.2 Socio-economic Context - Demographic Profile

Basic facts about the demographic status of the Region of Central Macedonia (which has an area of 18810 Km²) are shown in Table 15: Greek UC: Demographic profile., Table 16, Table 17 and Table 18.

Table 15: Greek UC: Demographic profile.

Partner	Region of Central Macedonia
Population	1872102 (2020)
Population density	101.2 /Km ² ¹⁸ (2019)

Table 16: Greek UC: Population details by age group.

Age group ¹⁹	Share (%)	Total
0-14	14%	267001
15-64	63%	1170080
65-74	11%	203021
75+	12%	232000

Education²⁰

Basic facts about education in the Region of Central Macedonia are shown in Table 17 below:

Table 17: Greek UC: Education level in 2019

Education Level	Share (%)	Total
Low	25.7 %	481130
Medium	31.5 %	589712
High	42.8 %	801260

Employment

In Table 18 the employment statistics are presented.

Table 18: GR UC: Employment Statistics for Central Macedonia²¹

¹⁸ <https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets/gngfvpqmfu5n6akvxqkpw?locale=en> (Population density by NUTS 3 region)

¹⁹ The age groups in Tables 16 and 18 are not the same with the corresponding Tables of rest UCs because appropriate information was not found based on the same age groups

²⁰ Population by educational attainment level, sex and NUTS 2 regions (%), last update 25.02.2021, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EDAT_LFSE_04/default/table?lang=en

²¹ <https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics/-/publication/SJO01/->

Age group	Share (%)	Total
15-24	3%	21.077
25-54	79%	503.108
55+	18%	114.635

Today, the primary sector (agriculture, livestock, and greenhouse crops) constitutes the main occupation of the inhabitants at a percentage of 38%. Crafts and industries operate in the Municipality of Vasilika, while in mountain settlements there are goat-sheep-breeding and cattle-breeding units. Also, noteworthy is the effort of the Women's Agricultural Cooperative of Agios Antonios and of the village of Monopigado, which produces traditional high-quality products with recipes that reflect the cultural heritage of the place.

4.2.3 Co-existing Services

While the pilot focuses on elderly caregiving, showcasing how beneficial state-of-the-art technologies can be, there is a potential to enhance connectivity and processing capabilities in farming, to address the demand in the area. The primary sector of development (agriculture, greenhouse crops, animal husbandry) in the municipal unit of Vasilika, constitutes the main employment in the area in which the pilot will be executed. In Vasilika, there are about 2 Km² of greenhouses, with the main crops being pumpkins and tomatoes. The Agricultural Cooperative of Vasilika has already proceeded with the construction of a packaging plant for the produced agricultural products. Also, flower species are cultivated and there are nurseries of vegetable species.

4.3 Evolution

The ageing of the population has serious consequences for society and puts pressure on health systems worldwide. Keeping people healthy and independent at home for longer is a major social challenge today. In particular, in the case of Central Macedonia, people over 60 years of age make up 35% of the total population. The expected development of this use case would be to attract all and more older adults to have eHealth robot companions at home, which would result in a larger infrastructure footprint requirement. Depending on the usage of resources because of other services uptake (e.g., video streaming) by other people in the vicinity, the infrastructure could require upgrades in order to cope with additional demand.

4.4 Demonstration Storyline

After the system has been installed and successfully connected to the internet, e-Health robot is going to show available categories that elder user wants to follow through specific sessions. After that, the selection device schedules every day an agenda with interventions for the elder user. As the older adult wakes up and moves to the room that the e-Health robot is located, it projects a day insight with some advice. If the older adult is on the same room, the device is going to propose some interventions according to the categories that choose from coffee session. The agenda also contains a recipe recommender that contains several recipes focused on fibres, and then can see the ingredients and the steps of making food. Also, if device perceives that the older adult sits for too long can propose some physical exercise or if the weather is good can propose to take a stroll.

On the next day, a daily agenda is being reshaped and different interventions are scheduled. Although the day insights remain, additionally a quiz may come up with some possible answers, and the older adult can choose what he considers correct, and which is focused according to the category. The device can also propose some exercises for cognitive enhancement. At first, a video is shown with a craft; when the video is over, the older adult should put in the correct order 4 images that relate to the video that was just played, in a specific time duration.

In another day, system can also propose to attend to some virtual workshops that related to older adults' interest.

4.5 Envisioned Solution

4.5.1 Technology Mixture

CAPTAIN Box is a standalone device, analysing and responding to user's behaviour, by conducting most of the signal processing tasks locally, eliminating as much as possible the need for cloud services. Based on Linux, its functionality is supported by micro-services carefully designed from central processing unit (CPU) and random access memory (RAM) resources use point of view. Even the fact that the components run independently from each other, they cooperate at a higher level to ensure enough processing power when needed as well as a balance CPU usage which leads to a CPU temperature lower than the CPU throttling threshold.

- Cloud services are used for collecting, curating, and processing anonymised data (profiling, clustering, and modelling) as well as for the plugins' marketplace, while local processing algorithms are used for non-anonymised data. The shift towards local processing services rather than cloud-based ones ensures a higher level of compliance with general data protection regulation (GDPR) which is a high priority objective for CAPTAIN COACH. The most demanding services in terms of CPU and RAM are those which perform image analysis processing to detect persons (17 human body joints are detected) and their emotions, as well as speech generation (text-to-speech) and speech recognition (speech-to-text) along with emotion extraction from speech. The former analysis takes place locally, while the speech related ones make partially use of existing cloud services. More specifically, the Speech Generation relies completely on cloud services while the speech recognition uses cloud services only when the local analysis could not provide accurate results. In the case of speech generation, the system is designed not to disclose any personal or sensitive information, while in the speech recognition case additional conditions are applied to minimize the information sent out of the device. The emotion analysis both from image and speech run locally.
- All the micro-services are connected through a communication bus in a loosely coupled architecture following a publish/subscribe (pub/sub) messaging model that decouples event producing services from event consuming ones. The pub/sub pattern is based on message queuing telemetry transport (MQTT). The messages' structure is well-defined and available to third-party components for connecting to the system by publishing/subscribing to relevant topics. The core components to support the communication among all the services are an MQTT broker and a MongoDB document database (both running locally).
- **Communication bus:** The MQTT broker is implemented by EMQ X (an open-source erlang/enterprise/elastic MQTT broker) running in a docker container. It is one of the faster and more reliable real-time brokers, providing MQTT functionality also through web sockets and a rest application programming interface (API).

- **Audio image processing service:** This is one of the main sensing services, utilizing the red-green-blue (RGB) camera and the microphone. Every camera frame is analysed for detecting any person in the field of view. If no person is detected for more than 3 minutes, the service stops analysing frames for detecting persons until a frame is 'different' from the previous one. The ML model (Posenet) to estimate the pose of a person from an image by estimating the spatial locations of key body joints is based on TensorFlow. Pose estimation refers to computer vision techniques that detect human figures in images. The nature of the input (2D image) leads to 2D location of the human joints, missing the depth information. Calculating the distance between the eyes and the nose, the service manages to estimate the person's relative depth. Once a person is detected in a virtual area (home structure configured during installation) a user position event is published. The information of the person is published every 10 seconds so that any component can enter the user's presence mode. Once a person is detected, the microphone is enabled for the next 3 minutes in order to detect any voice and extract user intent (represented as commands) that will be used from the coach to interact with the user in the state of listening to the microphone, the service captures maximum 2 seconds of sound (above a volume threshold) and publishes it to through the communication bus. The user is informed by a beep sound once the system enters the state of waiting voice input. The service shares the multimedia files as events by sharing the uniform resource locator (URL) of a local http server. Also, the service provides API commands for intuitively configuring and calibrating the image and audio components.
- **Speech synthesis service:** Speech to text relies on Google text-to-speech cloud service. Once a message is received from the text-to-speech service, it is checked whether the text is among those that are used regularly. In that case, if the corresponding audio file is already cached from a previous request is served. In the opposite case, the system connects to the Google text-to-speech cloud service and gets the corresponding audio file. Text that has been requested several times (above threshold) and converted to relative audio file is stored so it can be accessible without using the Google cloud service. The audio files are served through a http server hosted by the m07-text-to-speech service. As for the personal data protection concerns, the system does not include any personal data in the text to be transformed.
- **Speech recognition service:** The speech-to-text service relies both on offline and online engines. Each sound, is filtered to remove the noise if needed and is initially fed in the local speech-to-text engine. This offline engine is designed to utilise the DeepSpeech engine. DeepSpeech is an open source embedded (offline, on-device) speech-to-text engine which can run in real time on devices ranging from a Raspberry Pi 4 to high power graph processing unit (GPU) servers. DeepSpeech uses Google's TensorFlow to make the implementation easier. The pre-trained models that have already been integrated support English, Spanish, Italian, Greek and German while there are more options available. If DeepSpeech engine does not recognise any of the configured keywords, the service utilises the Google speech recognition cloud service. While running, the service collects a lot of sounds generated by the **audio image processing service**. The sounds to be analysed are fed to a stack and the latest one is processed first (last in-first out). If speech is recognized, the system clears all the pending sounds to increase the user experience in terms of responsiveness. When speech is processed, but no user intends (represented as keywords) are detected, the system provides beep feedback to let the user know that her/his speech was not recognized. The service also extracts emotion from the user's voice, applying offline the OpenVokaturi 3.0.
- **User model service:** The scope of the user model is to gather information about the user on a daily basis schedule that are mostly produced from the sensing part. User model is used for getting higher level

analytics from user behaviour and also help in the assessment. It contains information like daily emotion profile, preferred areas inside the house, gait analytics, and user Intervention Profiles for different domains of interest (e.g., physical, cognitive, social).

- **Contextual activity recognition service:** The overall architecture of the algorithm is that the system collects lower-level information from the sensors and extracts different levels of user and environment states. The user states refer to what movements and actions the user is performing while the environment state refers to the room and areas that the actions are performed, the time of the day and external sounds that are captured.
- **Projector service:** Exposes the functionality of the micro-projector by enabling other components to turn on and off the projection and change its brightness. The same service protects the projector by turning it off after 20 minutes of inactivity.
- **Device health status service:** This service monitors the hardware of the device, ensuring that internet and/or Wi-Fi connection is up and running, as well as the status and the up-time of the CAPTAIN COACH service. The service ensures also that the device will not enter any power sleep mode.
- **Broker service:** When enabled, and after alerting the user, this service enables remote configuration of the system from a technical person without allowing access to personal or sensitive information.
- **Environment service:** Publishes useful information about current weather as well as a forecast for the next 2 days based on data from openweathermap API. In addition, the service applies some rules to the forecasted weather information to provide indexes of the appropriateness of the weather for outdoor activities.

4.5.2 System Level Topology

Figure 10 shows a diagram of a system level topology, where CAPTAIN Box devices could connect to a 5G network that could be used for the Greek UC. The network is essential to communicate and synchronise data with CAPTAIN's Server and also use the capabilities of the Text-to-Speech from Google Cloud. The alternative connectivity is to establish an independent dongle 5G module for each CAPTAIN Box device.

Figure 10: Greek UC: Captain Box synchronises with server.

4.5.3 Sequence Diagram – Service Interactions

Figure 11 shows the sequence diagram where synthesises the CAPTAIN’s Box device as edge computing with the most major services provided to the user and all operations and processing running locally. The collected data are transferred through 5G connectivity to the CAPTAIN’s server, where all collected anonymised data are analysed further. Also, for each new software update for the device or new content for the user is achieved through synchronisation with the server, which is necessary on a daily basis. Also, users will be given the possibility of livestreaming of various actions and events for the user's education.

Figure 11: Greek UC: Sequence diagram.

4.6 Requirements

4.6.1 Functional Requirements

A list of functional requirements that are considered in this UC is provided below.

- The projector of the CAPTAIN Box device SHOULD appear the CAPTAIN’s logo when is powered on and ready.
- When the CAPTAIN Box device connects to the sound speaker, a confirmation sound SHOULD be sounded.
- When the CAPTAIN Box device shows a projecting content different than CAPTAIN’s logo, user SHOULD be able to hear the shown content.
- User SHOULD be able to interact with the CAPTAIN’s Box device through voice commands.
- CAPTAIN Box device MUST be connected to internet.
- Voice commands that the user can say MUST be shown through the CAPTAIN’s Box projector.
- CAPTAIN Box device SHOULD analyse and process the voice command of the user to text and show corresponding content.
- If the CAPTAIN Box does not receive any voice command by the user SHOULD be close and terminate current projection.
- CAPTAIN Box device SHOULD ask if the user wants to proceed with any scheduled interventions.

- CAPTAIN Box device SHOULD synchronise with CAPTAIN's Server to get all latest data.
- CAPTAIN Box device MUST show every day to the user the scheduled interventions.
- CAPTAIN Box device MUST ask user's opinion about the completed intervention.
- CAPTAIN Box device MUST analyse user's feedback and scheduled next day agenda.

Moreover, the equipment planned to be used in the pilot is presented:

CAPTAIN Box device (eHealth Robot) consists of:

- Computation segment:
 - Raspberry Pi 4 Model B
 - CPU: 4 cores. Broadcom BCM2711, Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.8GHz
 - RAM: 8GB
 - Disk: MicroSD 64GB Class 10 U3 V30 A1 UHS-I
 - Micro-projector DLP® LightCrafter Display 2000 Evaluation Module (EVM)
 - Soundspeaker Xiaomi Mi Pocket 2
- Network segment:
 - Embedded Wi-Fi adapter
 - 5G DONGLE Module
 - Quad antennas
 - USB3.1 port
 - Aluminum Alloy Heatsink
 - M.2 Key B Interface
 - SIMCom Module - SIM8202G-M2

4.6.2 Non-functional Requirements

A list of non-functional requirements for this UC follows:

- The CAPTAIN Box device SHOULD be placed in a room of the older adult's home, that the user is more active.
- The CAPTAIN Box device MUST be placed near a wall where its content can be shown to the user.
- The CAPTAIN Box device MUST be powered on throughout the day and MUST not be powered off by the user.
- The camera from CAPTAIN Box device should be directed to an area of the room that the person frequents most.
- The sound speaker from CAPTAIN Box should be powered on throughout the day and MUST not be powered off by the user.

4.6.2.1 Socio-economic

In Table 19 the corresponding socio-economic requirements are shown.

Table 19: Greek UC: Socio-economic requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Accessibility	SHOULD	The system should present the information in a comprehensible and interpretable way.
Data collection	SHOULD	The system should collect data in local level and pseudo anonymised when are synced with server
Analysing data	MUST	Collected data must be analysed without being able to backtrack user
Security	MUST	Access to the system must not be allowed within the network
Device monitoring	SHOULD	The system ports should not be blocked by the network firewall

4.6.2.2 Environmental (including Terrain/Topology)

In Table 20 the corresponding environmental requirements of Captain Box are presented.

Table 20: Greek UC: Environmental requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Temperature resistance	MUST	The device must be able to operate up to 95°C
No water resistant	MUST	The device is not waterproof, water must not fall on it
No anti-vibration	MUST	The device must not be dropped or hit by other objects

4.6.2.3 Performance – Key Performance Indicators

Finally, in Table 21 the performance KPIs with corresponding target values are provided.

Table 21: Greek UC: KPIs.

KPIs	Description	Specific Target
Network latency	Measure the E2E round-trip time (RTT) of data exchanged by pinging different point of the network infrastructure (in sec).	1-5 sec
Network throughput	Obtain measurements of the downlink/uplink communication link bandwidth (in Mbps).	≤ 50 Mbps
Resource utilisation	Monitor CPU/GPU/RAM usage of processing devices.	CPU Usage: 45% RAM Usage: 3GB of 8GB

E2E response time	Time between user request generated and service response received at the user (in ms).	< 100 ms
Processing response time	Measure the time that a processing device needs to process the data	TBD
Power consumption	Power consumption of infrastructure (in KW.h)	0.13 KW.h/per day
Service availability	Ratio of time the service is responsive and available to users (%)	99.9%
Service reliability	Percentage of successfully processed data within the expected processing time (%)	99.9%
Scale	Total number of end devices	10 CAPTAIN Boxes (one in each home)
Coverage	Served geographical area (in Km ²)	70 Km ²
Cost	Cost of infrastructure (in €)	About 1K €

4.7 Societal Requirements

4.7.1 Societal and Technology Readiness Level

SRL5 and TRL6

4.7.2 Organigram

- Professor Panagiotis Bamidis, Chairman of the Advisory Board and Founder of CAPTAIN Coach P.C., bamidis@auth.gr
- Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Chief Executive Officer and Founder of CAPTAIN Coach P.C., evdokimosk@gmail.com
- Despoina Petsani, Senior Product Manager of CAPTAIN Coach P.C., despoinapets@gmail.com
- Nikos Athanasopoulos, Senior Software Engineer of CAPTAIN Coach P.C., nickolas.athan@gmail.com
- Chrysanthi Kiskini, Director of RDFCM, c.kiskini@rdfcm.gr
- Kyriaki Kissa, Head of the Department of European Union Projects of RDFCM, k.kissa@rdfcm.gr
- Asteria Boura, Staff member of RDFCM, xgain@rdfcm.gr

4.7.3 Site Specificity

The use case does not have site specificity.

4.7.4 Ethical Considerations & Social Innovation

The UC does not work with CSR guidelines or criteria.

4.7.5 ISO 26000:2010

The most relevant normative/ethical aspects of social responsibility, based on the use case selection, for the workshop(s) and according to organisational CSR are 6.8: 6.8.3, 6.8.6, 6.8.8

4.7.6 Social Conflicts, Use-case Related

No conflicts of interest or socio-political conflicts from stakeholders' groups are identified.

4.7.7 Vulnerability & Potentially Excluded Stakeholders

People with major mental or physical disabilities and illiterate people belong to vulnerable groups and excluded stakeholders.

5 UC 3: Remote Community (UK)

5.1 Baseline Functionality

On isolated islands, such as Scilly, numerous connectivity gaps exist due to patchy network coverage. Despite past efforts to implement 4G services, and more recently 5G, the network coverage on the island remains incomplete. Maximising the advantages of digitalisation and connected services requires ensuring network access in almost all parts of the island. While 5G has been rolled out in certain areas, there are still multiple "dead zones" where connectivity is entirely absent.

JS owns and manages Scilly Organics, a small-scale vegetable farm on the Isles of Scilly, UK. This organic farm will act as a demonstration farm in the project, showcasing connectivity solutions addressing the application requirements and needs of the farm. Particularly, to showcase the advantage of having a digital farm, precision agriculture techniques will be adopted. More precisely, soil, water and meteorological sensors may be deployed, creating in real time the digital footprint of the farm and its related operation. In addition, the owner is a provider of summer houses for tourists, a new sector for the local economy with great potential aiming to identify common opportunities for network coverage for the farm and touristic experiences during the summer months.

The Partners and their role in this UC are shown in Table 22.

Table 22: UK UC: Partners and their role.

Partner	Role
JS	UC site provider
CAFA	UC solution provider

5.2 Operational Environment

The location in which the UC will be presented is in the Isles of Scilly that are located in the Atlantic Ocean, 45 Km off the South West coast of mainland Britain. Details about the area are given below.

5.2.1 Terrain / Topology

The Isles of Scilly are located in the Atlantic Ocean, 45 Km off the South West coast of mainland Britain. The archipelago consists of 140 islands with 5 of them being populated – St Mary's, Tresco, St Martin's, St Agnes and Bryher. The total area of the islands is 16.37 Km² and the highest elevation is 51m. The Isles of Scilly generally experience moderate rainfall throughout the year. The rainiest month is November, with an average of 86mm of rainfall, while the driest month is May, with only about 29mm of rainfall. The rainfall rate is usually about 74.93 mm/h. Average wind speed is ranging from 13 mph to 21 mph across different months, with the higher speeds typically occurring in the winter months of December and January. The islands experience a fair amount of cloud cover throughout the year. June is the most humid month, implying significant cloud presence, whereas the least humid months are January, February, November, and December. Moreover, the test pilot is in St. Martin's and its distance from cellular tower is 3.49Km. The specific topology is shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13.

Figure 12: UK UC: The Isles of Scilly, the distance between the test farm and cellular tower.

Figure 13: UK UC: St Martin's island with the test farm location.

5.2.2 Socio-economic Context - Demographic Profile

The total population of the islands is around 2100, most of them being on St Mary's. The main sources of income on the islands are tourism, which accounts for 63% of all employment but around 85% of the economy, and agriculture, primarily production of cut flowers. The Isles of Scilly have been designated an area of outstanding natural beauty (AONB), and the natural beauty of the Islands have been a major draw for tourists over decades.

The median age is now 50 years old, meaning the Islands are demographically older than much of the South West region and the age distribution²² in Scilly Islands is presented in Table 23. There are also significant housing shortages, and yet a degree of second home ownership around 25% of all houses.

Table 23: UK UC: Population details by age group.

Age group	Share (%)	Total
0-14	15.2	333
15-64	55.7	1145
65-84	28.2	581
85+	8.6	177

Education²³

The main school for the islands is the Five Islands Academy, where 270 students study ranging from 4 to 16 years old. This school serves as a primary and secondary education institution, accommodating children from reception age (early years) through to the age of 16 (General Certificate of Secondary Education (GCSE) level). Additionally, there are primary schools (4-11) on St Agnes, Tresco and St Martin's. For further education (post-16), students often have to leave the Islands to attend colleges and universities on the mainland. This is a common scenario for many students living in remote or island communities.

There are also opportunities for adult education and lifelong learning, often facilitated by local initiatives (such as Lifelong Learning provided by the Council of the Isles of Scilly) or online learning platforms, accommodating those who wish to continue their education later in life.

Employment

Many jobs on the Isles of Scilly are seasonal and these jobs are often tied to the tourism industry, which is a significant part of the Islands' economy. Additionally, there are jobs in the local authority, fishing, farming, transport and gardening. The employment opportunities on the Isles of Scilly are influenced by factors such as the seasonal nature of the tourism industry, the size of the community, and the islands' geographical location.

²² Source: Isles of Scilly facts and figures - E06000053 - ONS and Isles of Scilly (Unitary District, United Kingdom) - Population Statistics, Charts, Map and Location (citypopulation.de)

²³ Considering that Isles of Scilly is a very small and remote community, appropriate information about education and employment considering different age groups was not found compared to the rest UCs

5.2.3 Co-existing Services

In the Isles of Scilly, while LTE and 5G are present, their coverage is inconsistent, especially due to the challenging terrain. There is a need to expand coverage to areas lacking direct line of sight to cell towers, benefiting both residents and tourists. The islands have a strong broadband connection through a subsea fibre optic cable, yet most premises lack direct fibre optic connections. This disparity highlights the need for improved mobile and broadband infrastructure to support sectors like agriculture, where digital advancements could greatly enhance farming practices. The future strategy includes addressing mobile network 'dead spots' and investing in resilient internet systems.

5.3 Evolution

Apart from the precision agriculture scenario that will be demonstrated, offering 5G coverage to the whole island has a wider impact to the local community. Ensuring that 100% of the island stakeholders can learn from (but not limited to) the local businesses in other sectors (e.g., outdoor recreation, clean energy), will realise the XGain initiative to offer improved services for agriculture, land management, and other businesses needing good and reliable outdoor connectivity.

The cost of the equipment for the demonstration will be covered by the project but an operating business model including the local municipality or MNOs (Mobile Network Operators) requires funding. There is a clear need in the local community to collaborate to cover parts of the island with no connectivity especially considering the needs that arise during the summer months with the rise of tourism at the island. Cross sectoral business models between agriculture operations and tourism needs will be investigated.

By using aerostats to provide 5G coverage for data collection, we save land that should be set aside to build a mobile mast. Collecting more detailed information from sensors can reduce CO₂ emissions, as the farmer does not have to drive the tractor to the fields so often. Social security is strengthened by the knowledge that even away from big cities, equal 5G communication is ensured.

Tourism, a vital sector for the Isles of Scilly, greatly benefits from enhanced connectivity. The influx of tourists during summer months, combined with the current patchy mobile coverage, highlights the urgent need for improved telecommunications. Better connectivity not only supports the tourist experience but also bolsters local businesses and services, from leisure activities to distance learning opportunities. This aligns with the broader goals of the XGain initiative, aiming to improve services across various sectors, including agriculture and land management, while also considering the unique challenges and needs of the tourism sector.

5.4 Demonstration Storyline

A series of sensors will be deployed on the farm, forming the input data sources for a digital twin that can be used for the optimisation of production such as optimised water management, temperature control, soil moisture and monitoring of the production quality. For the scenario demonstration soil, water, meteorological sensors, and cameras to monitor the field may be used. All sensors will be connected to an edge device where pre-processing of the collected data will take place. The connectivity between the edge and the core network will be expanded by the usage of aerial radio relay aerostats ensuring the connectivity till the next connected area of the island.

Apart from Scilly Organics farm, the expansion of the tested and validated solutions will be investigated for the whole island. This can be achieved by means of aerostats/drones that will provide adequate and extended

network coverage. Research conducted on the Scilly Organics farm site, being the initial testbed, will provide the means to calculate the volume of aerostats/drones needed to cover the whole island, aiming at 100% coverage of the area, ensuring that no one is left behind, sharing the lessons learned, and providing access of services to the growing parts to the overall community.

5.5 Envisioned Solution

5.5.1 Technology Mixture

Multirobot System, presented in Figure 14 integrates an advanced UGV (Unmanned Ground Vehicle) with an aerial drone.

- UGV features a robotic arm for embedding soil sensors and a high-capacity battery for data-intensive tasks, including GPU processing.
- The drone, launched from the UGV, is tethered for power and data, facilitating seamless 5G communication transfer to the UGV's system.
- Equipped for rapid drone retraction in adverse weather.
- The drone has a top-tier 5G Wi-Fi router for a 700m radius data transmission, and advanced RGB and NIR imaging systems for agricultural monitoring.
- Ensures direct cellular base station connectivity and relays data for complex computational tasks to cloud servers via 5G.

Figure 14: UK UC: Deployment illustration.

5.5.2 System Level Topology

Figure 15 illustrates a system-level topology. This setup involves a wheeled robot on the ground with edge processing capabilities. The robot is connected to a 5G router, which is attached to a drone. This system also incorporates user equipment like computers, mobile devices, and sensors, all integrated within the network. The drone and the ground robot are linked via a tether, ensuring a cohesive operational framework.

Figure 15: UK UC: System level topology.

5.5.3 Sequence Diagram – Service Interactions

Figure 16 shows the sequence diagram on how data from these sensors and devices is communicated within a 5G network framework. The principles shown include the pathways through which data travels from the point of collection to processing or storage nodes, emphasising the interplay between IoT devices, user equipment, and network components in a 5G environment.

Figure 16: UK UC: Sequence diagram.

5.6 Requirements

5.6.1 Functional Requirements

A list of functional requirements that are considered in this UC is provided below.

- The UGV **MUST** have a robust robotic arm
- The UGV **MUST** be equipped with a high-capacity battery and a GPU-supported computer for processing complex data.
- The UGV **SHOULD** efficiently place soil humidity sensors at a depth of 20-25cm for optimal measurement.
- The system **MUST** transmit soil humidity data to a cloud server for real-time monitoring and analysis.

- IoT sensors deployed in the field **MUST** transmit data accurately and consistently to the central server for processing.
- Farmers **SHOULD** be able to access soil humidity information via an Agri GIS server on both computers and mobile phones.
- The drone **SHOULD** be equipped with a 5G Wi-Fi router and advanced imaging systems for monitoring and crop damage assessment.
- The drone **MUST** establish a direct internet connection for high-volume data task transfers to the cloud server.
- The system **MUST** maintain a continuous and stable connection to the 5G network for real-time data transmission.
- The UGV and drone system **COULD** ensure minimal field damage and maintain soil fertility while reducing irrigation water usage.

Moreover, the equipment planned to be used in pilot is presented and especially the CAFA Multirobot System consists of:

- CAFA Analyser: UGV capabilities, robotic arm, high-capacity battery, GPU-enabled computer
- CAFA Computer Vision: power and a data cable, 5G communication transfer from drone to UGV's onboard system
- Drone: 5G Wi-Fi router; RGB and NIR camera

5.6.2 Non-functional Requirements

A list of non-functional requirements for this UC follows:

- Data generated or consumed by the drones **MUST** be inaccessible to non-5G users to ensure privacy and security.
- Servers **SHOULD** have the capacity to store large amounts of data, potentially used for training predictive machine learning models.
- The system **SHOULD** be designed to operate efficiently in varying weather conditions, ensuring reliable functionality of the UGV and drone.
- Equipment **SHOULD** be reliable and be easily serviceable. Being a remote location, downtime is going to be accentuated if engineers are required to travel to the site to fix any problems

5.6.2.1 Socio-economic

In Table 24 the corresponding socio-economic requirements are shown.

Table 24: UK UC: Socio-economic requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Accessibility	MUST	The system should be simple enough to be deployed by non-tech people.
Economic Impact	SHOULD	Demonstrate positive economic outcomes, like increased crop yields.
Efficiency	MUST	Aim to reduce labour and operational costs.
Social Impact	MUST	Improve connectivity for locals and tourists.

Workforce Management	SHOULD	Optimise human resource utilisation post-implementation
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5.6.2.2 Environmental (including Terrain / Topology)

In Table 25 the corresponding environmental requirements are presented.

Table 25: UK UC: Environmental requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Landscape	MUST	Visual impact must not be detrimental to the quality of the landscape
Noise	SHOULD	Noise impacts from any technical solutions should be minimal and unobtrusive
Weather and climate conditions	MUST	The factors that affect outdoor equipment include severe storms, rain and salt-laden winds. Equipment must be constructed to marine environment standards
Environmental Impact	SHOULD	The system should contribute to sustainable practices, like reduced fertilizer and water usage.

5.6.2.3 Performance – Key Performance Indicators

Finally, in Table 26 the performance KPIs with corresponding target values are provided.

Table 26: UK UC: KPIs.

KPIs	Description	Specific Target
Network latency	Measure the E2E round-trip time (RTT) of data exchanged by pinging different point of the network infrastructure (in ms).	<50 ms
Network throughput	Obtain measurements of the downlink/uplink communication link bandwidth (in Mbps).	30 Mbps
Resource utilisation	Monitor CPU/GPU/RAM usage of processing devices (%).	<70%
E2E response time	Time between user request generated and service response received at the user.	TBD
Processing response time	Measure the time that a processing device needs to process the data (in s)	1/3 s
Power consumption	Power consumption of infrastructure	TBD
Service availability	Ratio of time the service is responsive and available to users (%)	> 95%
Service reliability	Percentage of successfully processed data within the expected processing time (%)	> 95%
Scale	Total number of end devices	At most 5
Coverage	Served geographical area (in Km ²)	0.49

Cost	Cost of infrastructure (in €)	TBD
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5.7 Societal Requirements

5.7.1 Societal and Technology Readiness Level

SRL4 and TRL5

5.7.2 Organigram

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5.7.3 Site specificity

The use case does not have site specificity.

5.7.4 Ethical Considerations & Social Innovation

The UC does not work with CSR guidelines or criteria.

5.7.5 ISO 26000:2010

The most relevant normative/ethical aspects of social responsibility, based on the use case selection, for the workshop(s) and according to organisational CSR are: 6.5.4, 6.5.5, 6.8.3, 6.8.5, 6.8.7.

5.7.6 Social Conflicts, Use-case Related

No conflicts of interest or socio-political conflicts from stakeholders' groups are identified.

5.7.7 Vulnerability & Potentially Excluded Stakeholders

No vulnerable groups with minor representation in the stakeholder mapping (so far) and/or presence in the workshops are foreseen.

6 UC 4: Farming and Forestry (Lithuania)

6.1 Baseline Functionality

Forest monitoring and evaluation of certain properties (e.g., fire risk, pest infestation, drought affected areas, etc.) is envisioned as the service provided by the use case. The developed service is based on a multicopter drone equipped with high-end hyperspectral camera. Hyperspectral cameras provide valuable information, but collect a vast amount of data therefore a lot of processing power is required to extract and infer the results from the raw data. In certain cases, timing is much of importance since immediate action can be taken to eliminate the hazards and prevent losses and damages. When conducting hyperspectral research, a lot of time is used just to transfer the data from the camera to the processing unit. This precious time can be saved by using new connectivity technologies such as 5G. The envisioned service will be using 5G network to transmit raw or pre-processed data, thus providing results of the hyperspectral analysis to the end user much faster.

The potential end-users of the developed service include: private forest owners, fire prevention specialists, public bodies responsible for environmental and forest management, forest engineers, researchers, environmental agencies, etc. The stakeholder groups that could benefit from the developed service extend beyond the foreseen end-users and include farmers, rural communities, environmental NGOs, and others.

Multiple scenarios can be thought of in terms of how the developed service could be applied in practice. For example, the service can be used to monitor and investigate the fire risk of a certain forest, identify and evaluate the scope of illegal logging, distinguish a certain reason for the tree damages, monitor forest health, movement of wildlife animals, and many more. Most importantly, the service would ensure a much more timely reception of data from hyperspectral cameras.

The Partners and their role in this UC are shown in Table 27.

Table 27: Lithuanian UC: Partners and their role.

Partner	Role
ART21	Technology developer, service provider
Forest owner	Use case site provider (state's forests)

6.2 Operational Environment

In the context of this UC, the main relevant operational environment is Lithuanian forests. Details about the area are given below.

6.2.1 Terrain / Topology

In terms of terrain, the foreseen service will be developed and tested in non-dense Lithuanian forests, that provide an operable environment for drone flights. The grey area (South-East of Lithuania) in the map below (Figure 17) gives an overview of the forest area (Figure 18) that qualifies for the test flights. The aim is to scan the pine tree forests, whose usual height is around 30-40m²⁴, with drones whose usual flight is around 70m. Moreover, except from the terrain characteristics, in terms of weather conditions we have rainfall on average 650mm/year, wind reaches up to 22Km/h and the fog does not last longer than 3 hours in early mornings, which

²⁴ https://lt.wikipedia.org/wiki/Paprastoji_pu%C5%A1is

should not affect the data collection via drones. To sum up the availability of data collection and transmission is around 70% of the time.

Figure 17: Lithuanian UC: Area, in grey, for the test flights
[Source: <https://media.etaplus.lt/614c395bd1a84/regionai728.jpg>]

Figure 18: Lithuanian UC: Forest area
[Source: <https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/a/ae/Krausnick-Berge-06-VI-2007-214.jpg>]

6.2.2 Socio-economic Context - Demographic Profile

The developed solution covers a variety of possible end-users, thus it is difficult to identify the population density or such parameters as age characteristics. The solution could be obtained and used for a number of purposes. The UC deployment is planned in Lithuania over the forest covered terrain that would be bigger than 5 Km².

The potential end-users of the developed service include: private forest owners, fire prevention specialists, public bodies responsible for environmental and forest management, forest engineers, researchers, environmental agencies, etc. The stakeholder groups that could benefit from the developed service extend beyond the foreseen end-users and include farmers, rural communities, environmental NGOs, and others.

This UC, differently to other UCs, is not geographically limited to one particular region. Rather, it focuses on rural areas as such. In general, the rural areas in Lithuania, where the UC will take place, the socio-demographic characteristics are as follows. According to the national statistics, in 2022, out of 2.8 million residents of Lithuania, a third (901521) lived in rural areas and the population details are given below in Table 28.

Table 28: Lithuanian UC: Population details by age group.

Age group	Share (%)	Total
0-14	14.4	128912
15-64	66.9	597375
65-84	16.0	142531
85+	2.7	23795

Compared to the cities, residents in rural areas have lower educational levels obtained, lower employment level, lower income; higher share of population under at-risk-of-poverty. The tables below provide insights on the trends in rural areas in Lithuania for 2022, including educational attainment of the population (Table 29), employment and unemployment levels (Table 30).

Education²⁵

Table 29: Lithuanian UC: Education levels for 15+ years old in 2022

Education Level	Share (%)	Total (Thousand)
Low	17.1	129.6
Medium	57.9	438.2
High	25.0	189.0

Employment²⁶

Table 30: Lithuanian UC: Employment Statistics for Q1 of 2022

Age group	Share (%)	Total (Thousand)
15-24	8.5	35.2
25-54	68.2	283.2
55-64	19.6	81.3
65+	3.8	15.7

6.2.3 Co-existing Services

The expected co-existing services linked to our use case relate to smart forestry monitoring. Smart forestry monitoring takes advantage of widespread digital transformation and information and communication

²⁵ Source: Official Statistics Portal, 2023.

²⁶ Source: Official Statistics Portal, 2023.

technology (ICT) to automate forest monitoring processes. It aspires to become a model of best practices in the development of artificial intelligence (AI) and internet of things (IoT) solutions for forest-based businesses. Data transferring and connectivity (5G) play a significant role in this smart forest monitoring concept.

The potential use of AI, IoT and data transmission 5G technology in forestry covers areas such as:

- Forest monitoring and inventory - scan the forests for specific preservation purposes, identifying diseases, types of forest, etc.
- Forest sanitary protection - (il)legal forest cuttings, measure the cutting area, and match to the permission document area determination.
- Forest maintenance - track tourism in the forests, identify areas where the maintenance is needed, do preventive preparations, etc.

All the data will be stored on the remote servers with the possibility to visualise the data on the dashboards. As this will be done from outside, it can be transferred as a know-how bases to the local communities.

From the technological point of view, the operational model could be applied on the farming sites, mountainous terrain, or places where live streaming of the data might be needed.

6.3 Evolution

In the foreseeable future, the further spread of 5G connection coverage over rural areas in Lithuania is expected. Sostine region has the boarded with Belarus, so the monitoring of the forests might be extended to the boarded patrol service, with identification of illegal migration. By attaching the tested equipment to the fixed wing drone the coverage territory might be from 5Km² to 10Km².

6.4 Demonstration Storyline

Multiple scenarios can be thought of in terms of how the developed service could be applied in practice. For example, the service can be used to monitor and investigate the fire risk of a certain forest, identify and evaluate the scope of illegal logging, distinguish a certain reason for the tree damages, monitor forest health, movement of wildlife animals, and many more. Most importantly, the service would ensure a much more timely reception of data from hyperspectral cameras. Its usability in multiple contexts increase the prospects to assist different rural communities in solving their specific issues.

6.5 Envisioned Solution

6.5.1 Technology Mixture

Currently, there are two main scenarios envisioned with the first one taking the implementation priority and the second one is reserved as a fallback solution. The first scenario states that a direct data transmission through the 5G network is used while the second scenario relies on partial data processing on edge devices to reduce the amount of data that need to be transferred.

All of the technologies that are planned to be used and the corresponding scenarios are further described:

- Heavy lifting drone with capabilities of lifting camera and transmitter equipment for required length of time; (Used in both scenarios)
- Hyperspectral camera used to gather all the data required with mount to the UAV; (Used in both scenarios)

- Portable and relatively low power 5G transmitter coupled with a low power computing node used for camera and transmitter interconnectivity; (Used in the first scenario)
- Local, on ground, edge computing device used for primary data pre-processing computations and an attached storage device to store raw and pre-processed data; (Used in the second scenario)
- Local high-speed connection between UAV and edge device for in flight data transmission for closer to real-time computation capabilities; (Used in the second scenario)
- A data collection server and service for receiving the data transmitted from the field. Also used for data storage, backups, data structuring; (Used in both scenarios)
- Cloud computing server that is directly connected to the data collection server for running a full data processing pipeline and depending on the scenario data will be injected into the specific part of the pipeline; (Used in both scenarios)
- A server for AI model deployment and continuous development that uses Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) for much faster model computation; (Used in both scenarios)
- Server with an API access for sharing gathered data and results. All of the server may be deployed on the same or separate hardware or on virtual machines in a data centre; (Used in both scenarios)

6.5.2 System Level Topology

Figure 19 shows a diagram of a system to be applied for the Lithuanian UC. UAV as the carrier vehicle will carry the equipment: 5G router, hyperspectral camera (can be RGB, or thermal camera), a low power computation device (i.e., Raspberry Pi, Nvidia Jetson). The power source is the UAV itself and real time data transfer is done via the 5G providers radio tower. The data via the internet is stored on data servers that include computational capabilities, and AI modelling and training. After the data is set in the data “lake” servers it can be accessed via the API, web interface or other visualization.

Figure 19: Lithuanian UC: System level topology.

6.5.3 Sequence Diagram – Service Interactions

In Figure 20 below there is a diagram of the expected data transmission protocols and technologies used on a high level. The data collection tool is hyperspectral camera (can be changed to thermal or high resolution RGB camera), the data is transferred to the internet via a transitional low power edge device and a 5G router as a transmitter. Via the internet protocols TCP/IP the data reaches the data server, and is accessible for computational purposes. The last step is data visualisation or access point for the end user.

Figure 20: Lithuanian UC: Sequence diagram.

6.6 Requirements

6.6.1 Functional Requirements

These are the main functional parameters that were put forward when creating the use case scenarios:

- Hardware SHOULD have capable of collecting hyperspectral data.
- MUST have real-time data transfer from hyperspectral camera over 5G network.
- Data transmission MUST be over 5G on local 5G provider infrastructure.
- Data aggregation server is a MUST, to collect and store transmitted data.
- Hyperspectral data pre-processing SHOULD be included into a fully functional system.
- The system COULD include AI models that create predictions using gathered data cubes.
- API and other user interfaces MUST be included for accessing the processed data and final results.

Moreover, the equipment planned to be used in pilot is presented:

Computing device - NVIDIA Jetson Nano 2GB Developer Kit

1. UE Type: Micro computer
2. UE manufacturer: NVIDIA
3. UE SW version: Ubuntu 18.04.6 LTS aarch64 / kernel 4.9.337-tegra
4. Weight: 126 g

Far edge computing device - Synology NAS DiskStation DS420+

1. UE Type: Network-attached storage (NAS) Server
2. UE manufacturer: Synology
3. UE SW version: DSM 6.2.4-25556
4. Weight: N/A

5G router - Teltonika RUTX50

1. UE Type: industrial 5G router – DUAL SIM Card
2. UE manufacturer: Teltonika
3. UE SW version: RUTX_R_00.07.04.5
4. Weight: 710 g

Camera – Specim AFX10:

1. UE Type: Hyperspectral imaging camera
2. UE manufacturer: Specim
3. UE SW version: AFX10
4. Weight: 2.5 kg

UAV – DJI Matrice 600:

1. UE Type: Drone
2. UE manufacturer: DJI
3. UE version: Matrice 600;
4. Weight: 9.1 kg (with six TB47S batteries)
5. Batteries: 6x4500 mAh, or 6x5200 mAh, 22.2V or 26.3V

The only change in the equipment is that we might work on a drone AURELIA X8, instead of DJI Matrice 600 and the basic specifications follow:

- 45 minutes flight time
- advanced power system
- payload up to 8 kg / 17.6 lb
- flight range 5 km / 3 mi
- onboard toolkit

6.6.2 Non-functional Requirements

Main non-functional parameters are:

- Hardware SHOULD be capable of long enough flight times to gather required amounts of data.
- 5G connections MUST be fast enough for real-time transmission of data.
- Data storage servers MUST be capable of storing large amounts of data (eg. at least 10TB storage capacity) with enough backups and redundancies to keep all of the gathered data safe and accessible.
- Computation servers SHOULD be capable of processing hyperspectral data in a reasonable time. From raw data to final results in a few hours, for the data to be still fresh and more useful.

6.6.2.1 Socio-economic

In Table 31 the corresponding socio-economic requirements are shown.

Table 31: Lithuanian UC: Socio-economic requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Smart forest management	COULD	Reducing working hours spent on forest monitoring.
Forest areas	COULD	Increasing the forest area of the country for socio-economic sustainability.
Biodiversity	SHOULD	Preserving biodiversity in forests and enhancing the recreational potential of forests for socio-economic sustainability.
Wood	WOULD	Reduce wood loss due to forest fires.

6.6.2.2 Environmental (including Terrain / Topology)

In Table 32 the corresponding environmental requirements are presented.

Table 32: Lithuanian UC: Environmental, terrain and topology requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Weather and climate conditions	MUST	Flights require good weather conditions. The condition that could impede the tests includes: fog, dazzling light, clouds, wind and turbulence, rain, solar storms, temperature and humidity, snow, drizzle, lightning, hail, storm
Dense forests	COULD	Affects visibility and flying operation. Flights cannot be operated in very dense forests.
Restricted flying zone	MUST	Flights can only be implemented in areas where such activity is allowed. The limitations: state-border area, airport zones and military areas.
Other obstacles: electric wires	MUST	Obstacles like electric wires could affect the drone and the machines attached, which is why they must be avoided.

6.6.2.3 Performance – Key Performance Indicators

Finally, in Table 33 the performance KPIs with corresponding target values are provided

Table 33: Lithuanian UC: KPIs.

KPIs	Description	Specific Target
Network latency	Measure the E2E round-trip time (RTT) of data exchanged by pinging different point of the network infrastructure (in ms).	About 200ms
Network throughput	Obtain measurements of the downlink/uplink communication link bandwidth (in Mbps).	80 Mbps (uplink), 250 Mbps (downlink)
Jitter	Measure the variation in the delay of received packets (in ms).	<60 ms
Resource utilisation	Monitor CPU/GPU/RAM usage of processing devices.	CPU usage: 10 % RAM usage: 1.5 GB
E2E response time	Time between user request generated and service response received at the user (in s).	< 3s
Processing response time	Measure the time that a processing device needs to process the data	TBD
Power consumption	Drone battery capacity (in mAh)	2 x 22000 mAh (target to use less energy to increase the flight time to 30 min)
Service availability	Ratio of time the service is responsive and available to users (%)	>99%
Service reliability	Percentage of successfully processed data within the expected processing time (%)	>99%
Scale	Total number of end devices	At least 1 drone
Coverage	Served geographical area (in Km ²)	> 400 Km ²
Cost	Cost of infrastructure (in €)	40K – 150K € (Specim camera of about 100K €)

6.7 Societal Requirements

6.7.1 Societal and Technology Readiness Level

SRL6 and TRL6

6.7.2 Organigram

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6.7.3 Site Specificity

The use case does not have site specificity.

6.7.4 Ethical Considerations & Social Innovation

The UC does not work with CSR guidelines or criteria.

6.7.5 ISO 26000:2010

The most relevant normative/ethical aspects of social responsibility, based on the use case selection, for the workshop(s) and according to organisational CSR are: 6.5, 6.8

6.7.6 Social Conflicts, Use-case Related

No conflicts of interest or socio-political conflicts from stakeholders' groups are identified.

6.7.7 Vulnerability & Potentially Excluded Stakeholders

No vulnerable groups with minor representation in the stakeholder mapping (so far) and/or presence in the workshops are foreseen.

7 UC 5: Aquaculture (Croatia)

7.1 Baseline Functionality

The UC will demonstrate how an extended network infrastructure developed using long-range wide area network (LoRaWAN) and satellite communication can transmit data from offshore sensors to the central monitoring system. Particularly the sensors are connected to the receiver (stations floating on water, float/buoy aid) via underwater cables. Multiple nearby stations can be connected to a LoRaWAN network, where an edge device (Intel NUC) aggregates data, pre-process it, and transmits (either raw or processed) data to other existing platforms and monitoring services. The satellite IoT network of ASTRO will be employed to retrieve data from the edge device.

The service is a periodic data transmission of the water quality parameters in the environment where oysters are farmed. The availability of satellite data transmission will determine the data collection and transmission period. Farmers will be able to remotely monitor the water quality parameters and plan their farming procedures accordingly.

The primary stakeholders of the solution are the farmers of various aquaculture species. However, the developed system could also benefit research and academic institutions.

The Partners and their role in this UC are shown in Table 34.

Table 34: Croatian UC: Partners and their role.

Partner	Role
Farmer	UC site provider
Benco Baltic	UC solution provider
Astrocast	UC partner – satellite connectivity technology and service provider

7.2 Operational Environment

The farm on which the UC will be presented is on the outskirts of the town of Šibenik, around 4 Km from the city centre (see Figure 21). The oyster farm is located on both sides of Šibenik bay next to the Šibenik bridge. A more detailed analysis is provided below.

7.2.1 Terrain / Topology

The terrain in the close vicinity of the use case site can be regarded as plain since the use case is located in the Krka river estuary. The approach to the farms is mainly made via boats since a steep increase in the elevation at the bank makes it difficult to reach by land. Measured from the water surface to the bank's top, the elevation increase is around 50 m. The riverbanks are also grown over with vegetation such as shrubs and trees. The width of the Krka estuary at the use case site (oyster and mussel farm) ranges from 320 meters to 400 meters.

Moreover, we need to say that in the Šibenik area approximately 37.4 % of days in a calendar year are with rainfall. The monthly precipitation level ranges from approximately 46 mm (August) to 224 mm (November). The average annual precipitation rate is around 128 mm and the wind speed in Šibenik rarely exceeds 40 Km/h.

Figure 21: Croatian UC: The location.

7.2.2 Socio-economic Context - Demographic Profile

The demographic profile is presented in Table 35. The town of Šibenik has a population of around 42600 people, of which about 34000 live in the urban settlement. The population density of the town is 105.4/Km². The city is the tenth-largest city in Croatia with an area spanning almost 400 Km². It is an administrative, political, economic, social, and cultural center of the Šibenik-Knin County, which extends along the 100 Km-long coastline between the Zadar and Split Riviervas, extending up to 45 Km into the hinterland area at the bottom of Dinara Mountain. The town of Šibenik has one of the major ports of Croatia (along with Rijeka, Zadar, Split, Ploče, and Dubrovnik). It is essential for overall employment, business, and the city’s trade. Economic development is focused on trade, tourism, construction, and metal processing, based on small and medium-sized enterprises. Šibenik has a long industrial tradition in manufacturing aluminium products, steel constructions, and shipbuilding.

In accordance with the population census of Croatia (2021), the population statistics of Šibenik-Knin county are presented in Table 35.

Table 35: Croatian UC: The demographics of the Šibenik-Knin County.

Age group	Share (%)	Total
0-14	About 12.7	12331
15-64	About 60	57994
65-84	About 24	23205
85+	About 12.7	12331

As compared to the total population, the largest number of persons aged 65 and over are in the County of Šibenik-Knin (27.3%) and the average age in Croatia is 44.3 years (for women and men are respectively – 45.9 and 42.5).

Education

In accordance with the Croatian census of 2021, the education level of the population of the town of Šibenik-Knin county at that time is presented in Table 36.

Table 36: Croatian UC: Education levels for 15+ years old in 2021.

Education Level	Share (%)	Total
Low	About 20.4	17139
Medium	About 59	49563
High	About 20.6	17330

Employment

In accordance with the Croatian census of 2021, the employment level of the population of the town of Šibenik-Knin county at that time was as presented in Table 37. The self-employed group comprises people who fall under the categories of employers and own-account workers.

Table 37: Croatian UC: Employment Statistics

Age group	Share (%)	Total
15-24	About 5.9	1448
25-54	About 74.3	19688
55-64	About 18.8	4640
65+	About 1	241

7.2.3 Co-existing services

There are two main services which are currently directly related to the technological solution provided in the use case. These are remote aquaculture farming and water-quality monitoring. These two services can co-exist with the implementation of the same solution. However, additional services could also benefit from the connectivity solutions implemented in this use case. For example, various on-site sensors such as air quality or climate condition sensors, machinery control devices, etc., that also use LoRaWAN for data transfer can be connected to the same infrastructure. Digital security devices such as cameras or motion detectors can be implemented as well.

7.3 Evolution

The system is expected to be developed into a fully autonomous water quality parameter evaluation and data collection system. Such a system would require minimal intervention and a workforce for maintenance. The system would have the possibility to be expanded by including additional sensors that would enhance the capabilities of the system and provide more information for the enhanced overall picture of the farm

environment. The final product is envisioned as a modular system where users can switch between the needed sensors without additional modifications. Additionally, improvements in functionality (automation of the depth control, etc.) are a core part of the envisioned future of the system. The information provided by the system could also be used by environmental engineers and allow the monitoring of the ecosystem and its dynamics. The possibilities of such technological evolution coincide well with the changes in the population of the Šibenik-Knin county. There is a clear population decline in the area resulting in a reduced workforce. Therefore, systems with autonomous working modes can become much more sought after in the future.

7.4 Demonstration Storyline

A farmer installs a developed water quality evaluation system. Data is being gathered and stored on the cloud. The farmer gets up, and instead of putting on his working uniform and going to the farm, he opens his laptop or smartphone and logs into the cloud server. He observes the current readings of the sensors and notices a minor decline in turbidity. He looks at the data collected when he was sleeping and observes that the decline started in the middle of the night. With this information, the farmer plans his workday and includes the water mixing procedure in the work plan. By using the said system, the farmer is capable of much faster and more frequent reading of the oyster environment and improved planning of his day-to-day farming activities. Eventually, the yield of the farm increases.

7.5 Envisioned Solution

7.5.1 Technology Mixture

The currently envisioned scenario for the use case involves the data transmission from the off-shore water quality sensors to the on-shore receiving station via the LoRaWAN network. The edge computing device connected to the receiving station will aggregate the data and if needed will process it. Data from the edge device will be sent to the cloud storage (owned by Astrocast) via a satellite network. Depending on the inter-connection capabilities of the devices used in the use case, the technologies envisioned are such:

- Water quality sensors capable of evaluating various water quality parameters. At least three parameters will be measured. Water salinity, dissolved oxygen content, temperature, turbidity, ultrasound, and chlorophyll content will be evaluated in the best-case scenario.
- Water sensor data will be transferred via a cable to the low-power LoRaWAN transmitter.
- A transmitter will periodically send the sensor data to the portable, low-power LoRaWAN gateway on shore.
- The gateway will be connected to the edge computation device for data aggregation.
- The edge device will be connected to the satellite connectivity hardware, enabling satellite communication and data transfer.
- Sensor data using the satellite connection will be transferred to the cloud server.
- A dedicated user interface – a server with an API (Astrocast) grants the end user access to the cloud server where the sensor data can be viewed.
- End user views the data via an internet connection to the server.

7.5.2 System Level Topology

Figure 22 shows a diagram of a system level topology for the remote oyster monitoring system used in the use case. The system is using both the LoRaWAN and satellite connectivity. The system shown in the figure is divided into two parts separated by colouring. The ground-based devices are used for the on-site data collection, aggregation and simple processing (creating data packets for satellite data transfer). This part of the system can be varied by including more sensing devices, collecting additional parameters, as well as incorporating other services. The other part of the system is dedicated to the data transfer from the site to the data storage servers and further to the GUI where the data is visually presented to the end user.

Figure 22: Croatian UC: System level topology.

7.5.3 Sequence Diagram – Service Interactions

Figure 23 shows a sequence diagram of the remote water monitoring system. The system data transfer is straight forward as can be seen in the presented figure. Such sequence diagram is envisioned for the service of remote aquaculture farming and water quality monitoring. However, depending on the actual implemented system (number of measurement points, sensors, etc.) the sequence diagram at the LoRaWAN transmitter – LoRaWAN gateway could have more than one data stream. In such a case, multiple data streams could be coming to the LoRaWAN gateway.

Figure 23: Croatian UC: Sequence diagram.

7.6 Requirements

7.6.1 Functional Requirements

For a successful implementation of the use case, several functional requirements have to be met. These are:

- The system **MUST** be able to evaluate at least three of the following water quality parameters: turbidity, dissolved oxygen, salinity, temperature, ultrasound, and chlorophyll.
- The system **SHOULD** be able to carry out periodic collection of the data. Sensors **SHOULD** be able to collect the data multiple times per day. The satellite communication speed (data transfer limit) will determine the final periodicity of the water parameter data collection.
- The system **MUST** allow manual (envisioned) or **COULD** allow automated (best case) sensor depth control.
- The system **MUST** have the ability to establish LoRaWAN connection and data transfer between on-shore and off-shore points.
- The system **SHOULD** visualize the collected data in a way that it can be accessed from various internet-connected devices.

Moreover, the equipment planned to be used in pilot is presented:

- Satellite transmitter: Astrocast Astronode S
- LoRaWAN gateway: Aqualabo
- LoRaWAN transmitters: Aqualabo, Libelium
- Water sensors: Aqualabo, Eureka Water Probes
- Edge computing device: Intel NUC

7.6.2 Non-functional Requirements

Main non-functional parameters are:

- Water quality data COULD be open to (shared) the other farmers and interested actors (academia, NGOs, etc.) in the area.
- Sensors COULD be installed on a movable platform for an easy measurement point change.
- The system COULD be equipped with a winch for changing the depth of the measurements.

7.6.2.1 Socio-economic

In Table 38 the corresponding socio-economic requirements are shown.

Table 38: Croatian UC: Socio-economic requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Affordability	COULD	The system could be affordable enough to make sense for a single farmer or a group of farmers to buy.
Accessibility	SHOULD	The system should be simple enough to be deployed by non-tech people.
Serviceability	SHOULD	The system should be serviceable by the customer to keep cost of maintenance and downtime low.
Scalability	SHOULD	The system should be easily scalable to cover larger areas by adding more sensors with LoRaWAN transmission capability.
Openness	COULD	The system could provide an open platform to grant the interested parties access to the collected data.

7.6.2.2 Environmental (including Terrain / Topology)

In Table 39 the corresponding environmental requirements are presented.

Table 39: Croatian UC: Environmental requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Robustness	SHOULD	The system should withstand harsh environmental conditions.
Non-corrosive	MUST	The parts of the system submerged in saltwater must be resistant to corrosion.
Environment compliance	MUST	The system must be compliant with environmental protection regulations such as Natura 2000.

7.6.2.3 Performance – Key Performance Indicators

Finally, in Table 40 the performance KPIs with corresponding target values are provided

Table 40: Croatian UC: KPIs.

KPIs	Description	Specific Target
Network latency	Average E2E latency (for data to be transferred from sensors to the data storage server)	No more than 10 h.

Data volume	Measure the amount of water quality data transferred by the system (in Kb)	1 Kb per day (for one (for one satellite connectivity enabling device).
Jitter	Measure the variation in the delay of received packets (in ms).	About 25 ms
Resource utilisation	Monitor CPU/GPU/RAM usage of processing devices.	CPU usage: 10 % RAM usage: 1.5 GB
E2E response time	Time between user request generated at the dashboard and response – data provided to the user (in s).	< 10s
Processing response time	Measure the time that a processing device needs to process the data (in ms)	< 200 ms
Power consumption	Power consumption of infrastructure (in W)	About 50 W
Service availability	Ratio of time the service is responsive and available to users (%)	> 95 %
Service reliability	Percentage of successfully processed data within the expected processing time (%)	> 95 %
Scale	Total number of end devices	One farm with two sensor modules
Coverage	Served geographical area (in Km ²)	> 0.7Km ²
Cost	Cost of infrastructure (in €)	Baseline price 1675 € + price for different sensors (TBD)

7.7 Societal Requirements

7.7.1 Societal and Technology Readiness Level

SRL5 and TRL6

7.7.2 Organigram

- Martynas Velička, Project manager (all questions, on-site workshop organizer) of Benco Baltic, email: martynas@bencobaltic.eu
- Tomas Žeimys, Project manager (all technical aspects) of Benco Baltic, email: tomas@bencobaltic.eu

7.7.3 Site Specificity

The use case does not have site specificity.

7.7.4 Ethical Considerations & Social Innovation

The UC does not work with CSR guidelines or criteria.

7.7.5 ISO 26000:2010

The most relevant normative/ethical aspects of social responsibility, based on the use case selection, for the workshop(s) and according to organisational CSR are: 6.5.4, 6.5.5, 6.8.3, 6.8.5, 6.8.7.

7.7.6 Social Conflicts, Use-case Related

No conflicts of interest or socio-political conflicts from stakeholders' groups are identified.

7.7.7 Vulnerability & Potentially Excluded Stakeholders

No vulnerable groups with minor representation in the stakeholder mapping (so far) and/or presence in the workshops are foreseen.

8 UC 6: Livestock and Farming (Belgium)

8.1 Baseline Functionality

Farmer X has multiple pastures spread across a vast area around the farm. The cattle are grazing on the pastures or in nature reserves during summer to promote the natural behaviour and well-being of the animals. To assess whether the animals are doing well, have enough water and feed available and can rest in shadow areas, the farmer has to visit the pasture on a regular basis. This is a very time-consuming task, and the observation is only a snapshot.

By these momentary observations the farmer cannot fully assess the behaviour, health and well-being of all animals effectively. There could be a dominant animal in the herd that prevents the others from regular access to the drinking spot or resting areas. This can lead to impeded development of some animals and cause health issues.

Through installation of camera's and other IoT sensors such as flow sensor and radio frequency identification (RFID) antenna on the drinking bin the farmer will be able to observe his animals remotely. In addition, smart algorithms could analyse the data to provide the farmer with key statistics throughout the whole grazing period.

The Partners and their role in this UC are shown in Table 41.

Table 41: Belgian UC: Partners and their role.

Partner	Role
Farmer/EVILVO	UC site provider will be provided by both
EVILVO	UC solution provider.

8.2 Operational Environment

The solution will be operational on pastures in Flanders which are mostly flat, or slightly hilly resulting in a maximum height difference of a couple of meters. The technical solution of the UC will be demonstrated on pastures in the neighbourhood of ILVO (Figure 24, Figure 25) and the more detailed analysis is provided below.

8.2.1 Terrain / Topology

The ILVO site is located in the province of East-Flanders at a 10 Km away from the centre of Ghent and about 45 Km from Brussels. The area is characterised by multiple small towns and villages. The landscape consists mostly of smaller patches grassland and arable fields. In terms of meteorological conditions, we need to say that in area of pilot in extreme cases rainfall can be as high as 5mm/h, and wind speeds is of about 30m/s. However, typically there is about 70mm of rain per month and the average windspeed is about 7m/s and during the grazing season, i.e., from April until October, the temperature might vary between -3°C and 40°C (<https://www.meteo.be/>).

Figure 24: Belgian UC: The location.

Figure 25: Belgian UC: A snapshot of the farm.

8.2.2 Socio-economic Context - Demographic Profile

In Flanders (which size is 13624 Km²) there live about 6.6 million people with a high population density (492 /Km²). About 22% of the population is older than 65 years old and about 16% of the population is younger than

14 years. The age group of 15 – 64 years represents 62.8% of the Flemish population. All these are presented in Table 42.

Table 42: Demographic composition of the population in Flanders.

Age group	Share (%)	Total
0-14	16	1087293
15-64	62.8	4257091
65-84	17.9	1210254
85+	6.1	412040

Education²⁷

In Flanders about in 2022 18.5% (785.542) of the 15- to 64-year-old population has a low education, 39.8% has a medium education and 41.6% has a high education, shown in Table 43.

Table 43: Belgian UC: Education level of the population in Flanders.

Education Level	Share (%)	Total
Low	18.5	785542
Medium	39.8	1681282
High	41.6	1756644

Employment²⁸

In Flanders 31.9% of the population between 15 and 24 years is employed, in the age group of 25-54 years employment is 86.9% and in the age group 55-64 61.7% of people are employed. Less than 1% of the activate population is working in agriculture. These are presented in Table 44.

Table 44: Belgian UC: Employment Statistics of the population in Flanders

Age group	Share (%)	Total
15-24	31.9	237782
25-54	86.9	2238204
55-64	61.7	577563

The pasture areas will be in a lower population density compared to the Flemish average. There might be houses in the neighbourhood, but the pasture is further away from the farm itself. The areas on which the solution will be rolled-out are private areas. Especially, as shown in Table 45, the number of farmers in Flanders is steadily decreasing, especially the young farmers (age < 40). Over the last decade, about 6% of the 29000 farmers stopped their activity. Only the age group of elderly farmers (>65) is increasing, and makes up about 25% of the Flemish farmers.

²⁷ Source: <https://bestat.statbel.fgov.be/bestat/crosstable.xhtml?view=631b4535-7a63-4695-967f-fe42238ee9af>

²⁸ Source: <https://bestat.statbel.fgov.be/bestat/crosstable.xhtml?datasource=f0487d44-2b45-427c-b2ce-890196a728c4>

Table 45: Belgian UC: Population having a company registration number in agriculture

Category	Share (%)	Total
< 40 years	15	4062
41 – 64 years	61	16702
> 65	23	6387

8.2.3 Co-existing Services

The service in the use case will be developed and tested at the pastures owned by ILVO as well as at the pasture of a farmer in the neighbourhood. The region has a broad range of agricultural activities such as livestock production, arable cropping and horticultural production. On the fields of ILVO many agricultural services are being developed such as application of drones, autonomous robots, use of IoT sensors in the field. Besides, there are small nature reserves, owned by a nature preservation NGO, and many country roads around the pastures which are popular for hikers and cyclists.

8.3 Evolution

A commercial 5G network is being rolled-out in the whole area of Flanders and will be available to all citizens in the near future. Due to the relatively high population density the network will cover the complete area of Flanders. However, the true coverage will need to be tested.

In terms of the UC service, the expected evolution is that researchers will first use the tool to acquire more detailed data on animal behaviour in the fields, and when the tool is more developed also farmers can start to use it (cost-benefit needs to be clear first). There is also a trend towards less farmers with larger farms and more animals so there might be an increased demand for (alternative) precision livestock farming (PLF) technologies in general to optimise farm management. Additionally, there is also increased awareness on livestock health amongst farmers which could also drive the demand for effective tools and measures to ensure optimal animal welfare. However, there are also environmental concerns for livestock production in Flanders causing some farmers near nature reserves being obliged to halt their operations.

8.4 Demonstration Storyline

The farmer could have many pastures and can install at the most remote pastures a camera setup to monitor his cattle and save time. At the start of his day, he consults some key statistics on the behaviour of his herd, which were determined by video analysis of the animals. During the day, he can check live his animal through the video feed in the app. Through the combination of this information, he can determine whether he should visit the field or use his time on other important activities on the farm and do not spend time driving the far away pastures.

8.5 Envisioned Solution

8.5.1 Technology Mixture

Camera system powered by a solar panel or battery (for proof-of-concept) and a low-power edge-computing device (e.g., Nvidia Jetson AGX Xavier) to process the data locally and send via 4G key indicators to the farmer. If

5G is available video streaming will be made available on demand. Additional IoT sensors such as a water flow meter, an RFID antenna or tags for identification of the cow might be added to the system to augment the behavioural information. All data from the edge device will be sent to an online database which will be accessed through an API for visualising the data for the end-user.

8.5.2 System Level Topology

Figure 26 shows a system level topology of the described technology mixture in 8.5.1 to collect data about grazing cattle in the pastures and provide key insights into their health and welfare. The data collection will mainly be done by a camera system and potentially combined with other IoT sensors such as a weather station, RFID identification, or a water flow sensor. All data will be processed in the field by a Nvidia Jetson Xavier device or Jetson Nano. The edge device will also be responsible for transmitting the data over a public mobile connection to the data storage infrastructure, which will host a PostgreSQL database. The collected data could be accessed through an API hosted on the server and will be visualised in a mobile or web application to the end user.

Figure 26: Belgian UC: System level topology.

8.5.3 Sequence Diagram – Service Interactions

Figure 27 shows a sequence diagram of the technology mixture in 8.5.1 where the collected data is processed on the extreme edge by e.g., a Nvidia Jetson Xavier that will transfer key information to the server infrastructure that hosts an online database. The data in the database will be available to the end user.

Figure 27: Belgian UC: Sequence diagram.

8.6 Requirements

8.6.1 Functional Requirements

- A camera SHOULD be powered by a battery and solar panel
- An edge-computing node MUST be capable of processing multiple frames per second.

- The edge processing device **MUST** be able to process images at medium frame rates.
- A commercial telecom signal **MUST** be available to the edge-computing node to transfer the data.
- 4G **SHOULD** minimally be available.
- 5G network **WOULD** be preferred.

Moreover, the equipment planned to be used in pilot is presented:

- Industrial USB3 RGB camera with a global shutter, with 4mm lens in weather proof housing
- NVIDIA Jetson orin nano 8GB
- NVIDIA Jetson Xavier AGX
- RUT240 4G network router

8.6.2 Non-functional Requirements

Main non-functional parameters are:

- The system **MUST** be able to operate in bad weather
- The system **SHOULD** be made inaccessible to passing by hikers/inhabitants
- The system **MUST** be able to overcome a power outage
- The system **MUST** be prevented from theft
- The solution **SHOULD** be able to handle short periods of connection loss through local storage or buffering.

8.6.2.1 Socio-economic

In Table 46 the corresponding socio-economic requirements are shown.

Table 46: Belgian UC: Socio-economic requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Longevity	SHOULD	The system should be operational for long-periods of time (at least spring/summer/autumn) without maintenance to cover the whole grazing season.
Relevancy	SHOULD	Only relevant data should be presented to the end-user
Data Storage	MUST	Data must be stored in a secure and anonymized way.
Data Sharing	WOULD	In the future the acquired data would be made available through a data sharing platform if allowed by the end-user.

8.6.2.2 Environmental (including Terrain / Topology)

In Table 47 the corresponding environmental requirements are presented.

Table 47: Belgian UC: Environmental requirements and their priority level.

Name	Requirement priority	Description
Robustness	MUST	The solution must be able to operate in all weather conditions as given in 8.2.1
Accessibility	MUST	The hardware must not be accessible by third-parties

8.6.2.3 Performance – Key Performance Indicators

Finally, in Table 48 the performance KPIs with corresponding target values are provided.

Table 48: Belgian UC: KPIs.

KPIs	Description	Specific Target
Network latency	Measure the E2E round-trip time (RTT) of data exchanged by pinging different point of the network infrastructure (in ms).	100ms
Network throughput	Obtain measurements of the downlink/uplink communication link bandwidth (in Mbps).	<50 Mbps
Jitter	Measure the variation in the delay of received packets (in ms).	30ms
Resource utilisation	Monitor CPU/GPU/RAM usage of processing devices (%).	80%
E2E response time	Time between user request generated and service response received at the user.	<1.5 sec
Processing response time	Measure the time that a processing device needs to process the raw image and sensor data (in sec)	<1 sec
Power consumption	Power consumption of devices in infrastructure (in W)	40W for the measurement setup and processing devices (excluding server components)
Service availability	Ratio of time the service is responsive and available to users (%)	>95%
Service reliability	Percentage of successfully processed data within the expected processing time (%)	>95%
Scale	Total number of end devices	At least 1 farm with 1 measurement setup (camera + edge device + mobile data transfer capabilities)
Coverage	Served geographical area (in Km ²)	0.03Km ²
Cost	Cost of infrastructure (in €)	1350€

8.7 Societal Requirements

8.7.1 Societal and Technology Readiness Level

SRL4 and TRL6

8.7.2 Organigram

- Jarissa Maselyne, Senior researcher (supervision, organisation of workshops) of EVILVO, email: jarissa.maselyne@ilvo.vlaanderen.be
- Jérémie Haumont, Junior researcher (development of technical solution, organisation of workshop) of EVILVO, email: jeremie.haumont@ilvo.vlaanderen.be

8.7.3 Site Specificity

The use case has site specificity. Although, placing one camera at the drinking bin might be easily replicated, there will be pasture that will be inference with other infrastructure such as roads, pastures from other farmers etc. Therefore, the placement of the camera should be evaluated from field to field.

8.7.4 Ethical Considerations & Social Innovation

The UC does not work with CSR guidelines or criteria.

8.7.5 ISO 26000:2010

The most relevant normative/ethical aspects of social responsibility, based on the use case selection, for the workshop(s) and according to organisational CSR are: 6.5.4, 6.5.6, 6.7.3, 6.8.4, 6.8.5, 6.8.6

8.7.6 Social Conflicts, Use-case Related

No conflicts of interest or socio-political conflicts from stakeholders' groups are identified. However, at this moment there is a conflict between livestock farmers and government / nature organisation due to debates about more strict environmental regulations.

8.7.7 Vulnerability & Potentially Excluded Stakeholders

Farmers who are not a member of agricultural cooperations or are less digitally skilled will be harder to reach and inform about the new developments.

9 Conclusions

In this deliverable, a thorough collection of UC requirements and specifications for connectivity and edge technology enablers is conducted. Moreover, information about the pilots' operational environment, such as the most important characteristics of topology and weather conditions is collected. Additionally, the demographic profile, co-existing services and (non-)functional requirements are provided. Finally, specific target values of technical KPIs are presented for the cases that are known at the time of writing this deliverable, and societal requirements are shown.

This detailed information for the 6 UCs of XGain constitutes the basis for the design of testing scenarios and the specific equipment that will be used 'in field' trials in WP5. Moreover, the collected information about connectivity and edge computing technologies, topology and weather conditions for all UCs will help the design of KFT in terms of the inputs that are needed to make appropriate system's propositions to the users of it.